

ABSTRACT BOOK

Bio⁴ Expanding The Horizon

The International Bioscience Conference
and the 9th Joint International
PSU-UNS Bioscience Conference 2024

October 28-29, 2024

Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University

Content

	Page
Introduction	1
Welcome Speech By Professor Dr. Anchana Prathep	2
Opening Remarks By Asst. Prof. Dr. Niwat Keawpradup	4
Faculty of Science Map	5
Scientific Program	7
Keynote Speaker	
KN1 Prof. Dr. Chatchai Muanprasat	Exploring Frontiers in Bioscience Research 12
KN2 Asst. Prof. Dr. Sara Bumrungsri	Ecosystem services of bats: Thailand perspective 13
KN3 Prof. Dr. Snežana Maletić	Organic Soil Amendments: Pollution Solution or Environmental Risk 14
KN4 Assoc. Prof. Dr. Surapong Chatpun	Sharing Experience with Staff Exchange in Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) 15
Invited Speaker	
INV1-T1 Prof. Dr. Bojana Bokić	Traditional use of mints in SE Europe 17
INV2-T2 Dr. Danijela Arsenov	Beyond Simple Food - Unveiling the Medicinal Benefits and Human Health Risks of Apiaceae Species 18
INV3-T3 Dr. Muhammad Danial Bin Che Ramli	From Forest to Pharma: The Potential Effects of Natural Products in Neurological Disorder. 20
INV4-T4 Prof. Dr. Purim Jarujamrus	Tailored Functional Nanomaterials as Peroxidase Mimics on Microfluidic Paper-Based Analytical Devices (μ PADs) for Innovative Point-of-Care Applications 21
INV5 Ms. Gordana Vlahović	Horizon Europe Funding Opportunities: Guidelines for Application 23

			Page
INV6	Mrs. Khobkhul Inieam	Erasmus+ Capacity Building in Higher Education (CBHE): opportunities for universities and staff	24
INV7	Ms. Ivana Pejović	Erasmus+ Projects: How to Get Involved? Navigating the Erasmus+ KA1 Mobility Program	25

Oral Presentation

Track 1: Biology, Environment and Climate Change

OR1-01	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Viviana Maresca	Pilot study on the use of two different environmental pollution bioindicators, moss and bee, in an area with a high cancer incidence	29
OR1-02	Dr. Milica Stankovic	From student exchange to climate change	31
OR1-03	Ms. Sirinya Sirimahawan	The quality of sea grape growth in culture pond related to the seasonal change	32
OR1-04	Ms. Umi Natar Shaharudin	Cytogenetics and genome size estimation of the narrow-lip <i>Spathoglottis Aurea</i> Lindl. (Orchidaceae) from peninsular Malaysia	33
OR1-05	Ms. Siti Nadia Binti Mohd Nizam	Survival strategies of epiphytic and lithophytic orchids: Exploring their ecological partnership with lichens in diverse ecosystems	34
OR1-06	Mr. Farhan Rashid	Morphometric analysis of <i>Spathoglottis plicata</i> and <i>Spathoglottis plicata</i> var. <i>alba</i>	35
OR1-08	Ms. Kwansuda Kongthong	Recycling fish scale waste into high value-added products	36
OR1-09	Mrs. Rubaiya Pervin	Impacts of fish cage farming on underlying sediments and macrofauna of Songkhla Lagoon System, Southern Thailand	37
OR1-10	Ms. Sinjai Phetcharat	Heavy metal concentration in seaweed and seagrasses from the Andaman coastal areas: A case study from Lidee Island and Libong Island	38
OR1-11	Ms. Phutita Wongwaiyut	A New Species of <i>Hipposideros</i> from Southeast Asia: Integrative Taxonomic Approach Reveals Cryptic Diversity	39
OR1-12	Mr. Pattanapong Jaisue	Increase in leaf greenness is an adaptive strategy of rice to P deficiency	41

Track 2: Biotechnology, Biochemistry and Functional Food

OR2-01	Dr.Nemanja Teslić	Green solutions for recovery of secondary metabolites compounds	43
OR2-02	Dr.Thunchanok Yaikhan	Genomic Characterization and Phylogenetic Analysis of <i>Enterocloster aldenensis</i> PSU25A: An Opportunistic Pathogen in Southern Thailand	44
OR2-03	Mr.Pavarish Jantorn	Colorimetric recombinase polymerase amplification for rapid detection of <i>Staphylococcus pseudintermedius</i>	46
OR2-04	Ms.jirasa boonsan	Thorough Screening of Potential Probiotics Using Nanopore Sequencing and Bioinformatic Analysis	47
OR2-05	Ms.Thitaporn Dechathai	Unveiling Mobile Genetic Elements: In-Depth Genomic Analysis of Multidrug-Resistant <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> PA12	48
OR2-06	Ms.Siriwan Kompramool	Genomic Analysis and Probiotic Characteristics of <i>Pediococcus pentosaceus</i> HN8 with a Focus on GABA Synthesis	49
OR2-07	Ms.Thanchanok Muangkaew	Phenotypic and Genomic Analysis of <i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i> MEDPSU_PRO_001 isolated from Chicken Feces, a potential probiotic with aggregation ability	50
OR2-08	Ms.Krittaporn Lempan	The Genetic Diversity and Population Study of Mahseer, <i>Tor tambra</i> and <i>Tor tambroides</i> Distributed in Thailand and Peninsular Malaysia	51

Track 3: Bioactive Natural Products and Biomedicine

OR3-01	Assoc. Prof. Dr.Fazia Adyani Ahmad Fuad	Exploring the Potential of Chitin and Its Derivative in Inhibiting the Human Hexokinase Isoform 2 Towards Developing Anti-Dengue Drugs	53
OR3-02	Ms.Piyapat Aiemcharoen	Biological Activities of Ethanolic Extracts From the Inflorescence of Kluai Namwa (<i>Musa ABB</i> CV. "Kluai Namwa")	54

Track 4: Bio-sensing Technology and Data Science

OR4-01	Mr.Predrag Lugonaja	A Decade of Crop Monitoring Through Remote Sensing: Insights into Climate Change Impacts on crop practice, case studies Vojvodina from 2013-2023	56
OR4-02	Dr.Mohd Zulhakimi Ab Razak	Design Challenges in the Development of Portable Peritoneal Dialysis Prototype Module in Malaysia	58
OR4-03	Dr.Atchara Lomae	Smartphone-enabled electrochemical point-of-care testing for SARS-CoV-2 detection	60
OR4-04	Dr.Suntisak Khumngern	Smartphone-enabled flow injection amperometric glucose monitoring based on a screen-printed carbon electrode modified with PEDOT@PB and a GOx@PPtNPs@MWCNTs nanocomposite	61
OR4-05	Mr.Thanawath Tuntiwongmetee	Enzymatic uric acid biosensor based on AuNPs-GO-CS porous cryogel coated on PB-PEDOT:PSS modified screen-printed carbon electrode	63

Poster Presentation

Track 1: Biology, Environment and Climate Change

P1-01	Asst. Prof. Dr.Bongkot Wichachucherd	Year-round Occurrence of Crustacean Holoplanktons in Mae Klong River Mouth as Indicator of Natural Food in Gulf of Thailand	66
P1-02	Prof. Dr.Slobodanka Pajević	Heavy metals accumulation (As, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, Cu and Cd) in vegetables grown on polluted soil and consumers health assessment	67
P1-03	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Adriana Basile	Combining the use of Mosses and Snails as Bio-indicators of Heavy Metal Air Pollution	68
P1-04	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Viviana Maresca	Protective effect of <i>Ocimum basilicum</i> L. essential oil on <i>Lactuca sativa</i> L. treated with cadmium	70
P1-05	Ms.Rapeepan Kongnual	Effect of Chronic High-Sugar Consumption on Behavior Adaptation in Mice	71
P1-06	Asst. Prof. Dr.Yurachat Meksuwan	Influence of Seasonal Variations on the Anatomical and Physiological Characteristics of <i>Launaea sarmantosa</i> (Willd.) Kuntze (Asteraceae) of the Andaman Coast, Thailand	72

			Page
Track 2: Biotechnology, Biochemistry and Functional Food			
P2-01	Ms.Gordana Vlahović (Asst. Prof. Dr.Anita Leovac Maćerak)	Acetic acid pretreatment effects on biogas production from sewage sludge	74
P2-02	Ms.Sirikan Suwannasin	Phenotypic and Genotypic Study Through Virulence and Antibiotic Resistance of <i>Enterococcus avium</i> MC09 from Mud Crab	76
P2-03	Ms.Nattarika Chaichana	The Whole Genome Analysis of <i>Mangrovibacter phragmitis</i> PSU-3885-11 Isolated from a Patient in Thailand	78
P2-04	Ms.Jaruwan Boonchuay	Germ cell grafting in banana shrimp for sustainable aquaculture	80
P2-05	Ms.Kuwanhusna Saroeng	Freezing for the Future: Cryopreservation Strategies for <i>Halophila ovalis</i>	81
Track 3: Bioactive Natural Products and Biomedicine			
P3-01	Mr.Danudate Tuntadapun	Lipid nanoparticles of germinated brown rice (<i>Oryza sativa</i> L. var. Sangyod) and chamomile (<i>Chamaemelum nobile</i> L.) to improve sleep quality and reduce stress in neurons (SH-SY5Y)	83
P3-02	Ms.pakavarin khunphet	Investigating Nucleus Accumbens Oscillations in Mice Following Acute MDMA Administration (10 mg/kg) Using LFP Recording	84
P3-03	Ms.Sutthisa Khwankaew	The Synergistic Effect of Lupinifolin and Antibiotics Against MRSA: A Potential Solution to Antibiotic Resistance	85
Track 4: Bio-sensing Technology and Data Science			
P4-01	Mr.Inarm Ekakkaraphibal	Development of No-Code Programming to Implement 3D Animation for Telerehabilitation of Therapeutic Office Syndrome	87
List of Conference Attendees			
	Presenters		90
	General Participants		100
Committees			103

INTRODUCTION

The International Bioscience Conference and the 9th Joint International PSU-UNS Bioscience Conference is a biannual international conference organized by Prince of Songkla University and University of Novi Sad. This year, we are delighted to announce the theme “*Bio4 Expanding the horizon*” to foster knowledge exchange and deepen collaboration during the in-depth discussion session.

The conference will be hosted by Prince of Songkla University at the campus of the Faculty of Science on 28-29 October 2024. We invite experts in the bioscience research field to share and discuss the latest research, innovations, and trends in the field. Holding the event in its own halls enables the Faculty of Science to comply with a more sustainable event management and allows all participants to gain first-hand impressions and explore our facilities. Hat Yai is a vibrant city in southern Thailand, known as the region's educational center, with bustling markets, diverse cultural influences, and serving as a gateway to Malaysia.

Professor Dr. Anchana Prathep

Dean of Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University
Chairwoman, 9th Joint International PSU-UNS Bioscience Conference
2024

October 28, 2024

Basic Science Lecture and Laboratory Building 3,
Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University

On behalf of the Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, it is an honor to welcome you to the International Bioscience Conference and the 9th Joint International PSU-UNS Bioscience Conference. We extend a warm welcome to our distinguished guests, esteemed speakers, and all participants joining us from various institutions and organizations. Your presence enriches this event, and we are privileged to host you.

This year's theme, *"Bio⁴ Expanding The Horizon,"* reflects our commitment to advancing collaboration and sharing the latest developments in Biology, Biotechnology, Biomedicine, and Bio-sensing Technology. The conference sessions are designed to foster knowledge exchange, and create opportunities for meaningful collaboration across these fields.

We are delighted to present four exceptional keynote speakers: Prof. Dr. Chatchai Muanprasat on Frontiers in Bioscience Research, Asst. Prof. Dr. Sara Bumrungsri on Bioscience Innovations for a Sustainable Tomorrow, Prof. Dr. Snežana Maletić on Organic Soil Amendments, and Assoc. Prof. Dr. Surapong Chatpun on Staff Exchange in the Horizon Europe Framework. Invited speakers will further enrich the program with discussions on topics from medicinal plants to nanomaterials, as well as insights into funded collaborative opportunities.

This year, IBSC is being held in Hat Yai, and for the first time, we are hosting such an international gathering at our faculty. With over 150 participants from six countries—Bangladesh, Czech Republic, Italy, Malaysia, Serbia, and Thailand—this event represents a shared dedication to tackling global challenges in bioscience.

This conference is a reality thanks to our partners and the efforts of our organizing committee, and we are proud to host it as a sustainable initiative focused on reducing our carbon footprint.

We encourage all participants to fully engage, connect, and explore new opportunities over these two days. May this conference inspire ideas and foster enduring partnerships. Thank you, and welcome to the International Bioscience Conference 2024.

Asst. Prof. Dr. Niwat Keawpradup

President of Prince of Songkla University
9th Joint International PSU-UNS Bioscience Conference 2024
October 28, 2024
Basic Science Lecture and Laboratory Building,
Room BSc3, Faculty of Science,
Prince of Songkla University

Distinguished guests, dear colleagues, and participants,

On behalf of Prince of Songkla University, we are delighted to welcome all distinguished guests, colleagues, and participants to the 9th Joint International PSU-UNS Bioscience Conference. This event unites us in the pursuit of knowledge and innovation in bioscience, underscoring the strong collaboration between Prince of Songkla University and the University of Novi Sad.

The conference theme, *"Bio⁴ Expanding The Horizon,"* invites us to deepen our understanding across areas such as environmental science, biotechnology, and health. It is inspiring to see researchers, academics, and students from six countries—long-standing partners and friends of PSU—gather to explore these critical topics.

I extend my gratitude to the Faculty of Science for organizing this low-carbon event, demonstrating a commitment to sustainability and environmentally friendly practices that serve as a valuable example. I am also grateful to our keynote and invited speakers, whose insights will guide our discussions and advance progress in the field.

I hope this conference sparks valuable discussions, inspires fresh perspectives, and fosters enduring collaborations. May it serve as a foundation for impactful connections and shared achievements in the field of bioscience.

Thank you.

Faculty of Science Map

1. Faculty of Science Administration
2. Pumpkin Building
3. Pre-clinic Building (PR)
4. Chemistry Building
5. Computer Science Building (CS)
6. Mathematics & Statistics Building (M)
7. Physics Building
8. Biology Building
9. Laboratory Animals Service Center
10. Multiple Laboratory (ML)
11. New Multiple Laboratory (NML)
12. Science & Technology Building
13. Princess Maha Chakri Sirindhorn Natural History Museum

14. Measurement and Standard Accreditation Center

15. Basic Science & Laboratory Building (BSc) : IBSC2024'S Venue

16. Learning Resource Center Building (LRC)
17. Faculty of Nursing
18. Faculty of Dentistry
19. Office of Digital Innovation and Intelligent Systems (DIIS)
20. Sport Complex
21. Faculty of Engineering

An aerial photograph of the Prince of Songkla University campus. The image shows several large, modern university buildings with white and grey facades and green roofs. In the foreground, there are lush green trees and a parking lot with several cars. In the background, there are rolling green hills under a bright blue sky with scattered white clouds. A yellow speech bubble is overlaid on the left side of the image, containing the text 'Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University'.

Faculty of Science,
Prince of Songkla University

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM							
Date	Time	Activities					
Oct 28, 2024	08.30-09.00	REGISTRATION					
	09.00-09.20	OPENING CEREMONY Prof. Dr. Anchana Prathep Dean of the Faculty of Sciences, Prince of Songkla University, Thailand Prof. Dr. Srdan Rončević Dean of the Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia Asst. Prof. Dr. Niwat Keawpradub President of Prince of Songkla University, Thailand					
		PHOTO SESSION					
	09.20-10.05	KEYNOTE SESSION 1 KN1 : Prof. Dr. Chatchai Muanprasat Faculty of Medicine, Ramathibodi Hospital, Mahidol University, Thailand Coordinator of BCG Frontier Research Cluster, PMU-B "Exploring Frontiers in Bioscience Research"					
	10.05-10.50	KEYNOTE SESSION 2 KN2 : Asst. Prof. Dr. Sara Bumrungsri Biology, Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University "Bioscience Innovations for a Sustainable Tomorrow"					
	10.50-11.15	COFFEE BREAK					
	11.15-12.00	KEYNOTE SESSION 3 KN3 : Prof. Dr. Snežana Maletić Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia "Organic Soil Amendments: Pollution Solution or Environmental Risk"					
	12.00-13.00	LUNCH					
			BSC0305 Track 1: Biology, Environment and Climate Change	BSC0306 Track 2: Biotechnology, Biochemistry and Functional Food	BSC0307 Track 3: Bioactive Natural Products and Biomedicine Track 1: Biology, Environment and Climate Change	BSC0308 Track 4: Bio-sensing Technology and Data Science Track 1: Biology, Environment and Climate Change	BSC0304 Poster Session
	13.00-13.30	INVITED LECTURE	INV1-T1 Prof. Dr. Bojana Bokić Department of Biology and Ecology, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia "Traditional use of mints in SE Europe"	INV2-T2 Prof. Dr. Danijela Arsenov Department of Biology and Ecology, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia "Beyond Simple Food – Unveiling the Medicinal Benefits and Human Health Risks of Apiaceae Species"	INV3-T3 Dr. Muhammad Danial Bin Che Ramli Management and Science University, Malaysia "From Forest to Pharma: The Potential Effects of Natural Products in Neurological Disorder"	INV4-T4 Assoc. Prof. Dr. Purim Jarujamrus Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Ubon Ratchathani University "Tailored Functional Nanomaterials as Peroxidase Mimics on Microfluidic Paper-Based Analytical Devices (μ PADs) for Innovative Point-of-Care Applications"	
13.30-17.00	Oral Presentation & Poster Presentation						
13.30-13.50	Oral Presentation	OR1-01 Assoc. Prof. Dr. Viviana Maresca Pilot study on the use of two different environmental pollution bioindicators, moss and bee, in an area with a high cancer incidence	OR2-01 Dr. Nemanja Teslić Green solutions for recovery of secondary metabolites compounds	OR3-01 Assoc. Prof. Dr. Fazia Adyani Ahmad Fuad Exploring the Potential of Chitin and Its Derivative in Inhibiting the Human Hexokinase Isoform 2 Towards Developing Anti-Dengue Drugs	OR4-01 Mr. Predrag Lugonaja A Decade of Crop Monitoring Through Remote Sensing: Insights into Climate Change Impacts on crop practice, case studies Vojvodina from 2013-2023	Poster Presentation	
13.50-14.10		OR1-02 Dr. Milica Stankovic From student exchange to climate change	OR2-02 Dr. Thunchanok Yaikhan Genomic Characterization and Phylogenetic Analysis of <i>Enterocloster aldenensis</i> PSU25A: An Opportunistic Pathogen in Southern Thailand	OR3-02 Ms. Piyapat Aiemcharoen Biological Activities of Ethanolic Extracts From the Inflorescence of Klui Namwa (<i>Musa ABB CV. "Klui Namwa"</i>)	OR4-03 Dr. Atchara Lomae Smartphone-enabled electrochemical point-of-care testing for SARS-CoV-2 detection		

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM								
Date	Time	Activities						
	14.10-14.30		OR1-03 Ms.Sirinya Sirimahawan The quality of sea grape growth in culture pond related to the seasonal change	OR2-03 Mr.Pavarish Jantorn Colorimetric recombinase polymerase amplification for rapid detection of <i>Staphylococcus pseudintermedius</i>	OR1-08 Ms.Kwansuda Kongthong Recycling fish scale waste into high value-added products	OR4-02 Dr.Mohd Zulhakimi Ab Razak Design Challenges in the Development of Portable Peritoneal Dialysis Prototype Module in Malaysia		
	14.30-14.50		OR1-04 Ms.Umi Natar Shaharudin Cytogenetics and genome size estimation of the narrow-lip <i>Spathoglottis Aurea</i> Lindl. (Orchidaceae) from peninsular Malaysia	OR2-04 Ms.jirasa boonsan Thorough Screening of Potential Probiotics Using Nanopore Sequencing and Bioinformatic Analysis	OR1-09 Mrs.Rubaiya Pervin Impacts of fish cage farming on underlying sediments and macrofauna of Songkhla Lagoon System, Southern Thailand	OR4-04 Dr.Suntisak Khumngern Smartphone-enabled flow injection amperometric glucose monitoring based on a screen-printed carbon electrode modified with PEDOT@PB and a COx@PPiNPs@MWCNTs nanocomposite		
	14.50-15.00							
	15.00-15.20	COFFEE BREAK						
	15.20-15.40	Oral Presentation & Award	OR1-05 Ms.Siti Nadia Binti Mohd NZam Survival strategies of epiphytic and lithophytic orchids: Exploring their ecological partnership with lichens in diverse ecosystems	OR2-05 Ms.Thitaporn Dechathai Unveiling Mobile Genetic Elements: In-Depth Genomic Analysis of Multidrug-Resistant <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> PA12	AWARD SESSION		OR4-05 Mr.Thanawath Tuntiwongmetee Enzymatic uric acid biosensor based on AuNPs-GO-CS porous cryogel coated on PB-PEDOT:PSS modified screen-printed carbon electrode	Award session Best Poster Award Popular Vote Award
	15.40-16.00		OR1-06 Mr.Farhan Rashid Morphometric analysis of <i>Spathoglottis plicata</i> and <i>Spathoglottis plicata</i> var. alba	OR2-06 Ms.Siriwan Kompramool Genomic Analysis and Probiotic Characteristics of <i>Pediococcus pentosaceus</i> HN8 with a Focus on GABA Synthesis		OR1-10 Ms.Sinjai Phetcharat Heavy metal concentration in seaweed and seagrasses from the Andaman coastal areas: A case study from Lidee Island and Libong Island		
	16.00-16.20		AWARD SESSION		OR2-07 Ms.Thanchanok Muangkaew Phenotypic and Genomic Analysis of <i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i> MEDPSU_PRO_001 isolated from Chicken Feces, a potential probiotic with aggregation ability		OR1-11 Ms.Phutita Wongwaiyut A New Species of <i>Hipposideros</i> from Southeast Asia: Integrative Taxonomic Approach Reveals Cryptic Diversity	
	16.20-16.40			OR2-08 Ms.Krittaporn Lempan The Genetic Diversity and Population Study of Mahseer, <i>Tor tambra</i> and <i>Tor tambroides</i> Distributed in Thailand and Peninsular Malaysia		OR1-12 Mr.Pattanapong Jaisue Increase in leaf greenness is an adaptative strategy of rice to P deficiency		
	16.40-17.00			AWARD SESSION		AWARD SESSION		
	18.00-20.00	WELCOME RECEPTION						

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM		
Date	Time	Activities
Oct 29, 2024	09.00-09.40	KEYNOTE SESSION 4 KN4 : Assoc. Prof. Dr. Surapong Chatpun Department of Biomedical Sciences and Biomedical Engineering, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University "Sharing Experience with Staff Exchange in Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON)"
	09.40-10.20	INVITED SESSION 5 INV5 : Ms. Gordana Vlahovic Head of International Relations, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia "Horizon Europe Funding Opportunities: Guidelines for Application"
	10.20-10.40	COFFEE BREAK
	10.40-11.20	INVITED SESSION 6 INV6: Ms. Khobkhul Inieam Program Officer, EU Delegation to Thailand "Erasmus+ Capacity Building in Higher Education: opportunities for universities and staff"
	11.20-12.00	INVITED SESSION 7 INV7: Ms. Ivana Pejović International Relations Officer, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia "EU/Erasmus+ projects: How to get involved?"
	12.00-13.30	LUNCH
	13.30-15.00	PANEL DISCUSSION SESSION
	13.30-14.30	GROUP DISCUSSION Group 1: Excellent Science & Dual degree for graduate studies and From Lab to Market Facilitator: Assoc. Prof. Dr. Pimonsri Mittraparp-arthorn Group 2: Global Challenges (Health, Food, Bioeconomy) and From Lab to Market Facilitator: Assoc. Prof. Dr. Decha Sermwittayawong Group 3: Global Challenges (Climate, Natural Resources, Agriculture & Environment) and From Lab to Market Facilitator: Prof. Dr. Anchana Prathep
	14.30-15.00	COFFEE BREAK & WRAP-UP PANEL DISCUSSION (10 minute/Group)

KEYNOTE SPEAKER

Keynote Session 1

Exploring Frontiers in Bioscience Research

Chatchai Muanprasat^{1,*}, Saravut Satitsri¹, Vatcharin Rukachaisirikul²

¹ Chakri Naruebodindra Medical Institute, Faculty of Medicine Ramathibodi Hospital, Mahidol University, Samutprakarn 10540, Thailand

² Division of Physical Science and Center of Excellence for Innovation in Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

* Corresponding author: chatchai.mua@mahidol.ac.th

Abstract: Understanding of disease mechanism is vital to the development of novel diagnostics and therapeutics. Chemical genetics using small-molecule functional probe of human proteins in conjunction with the use of relevant disease models has been proven beneficial in identification and validation of drug targets of human diseases. Using small-molecule inhibitors of chloride channels, cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulators (CFTR) and calcium-activated chloride channel (CaCC) has been validated as drug target for the secretory diarrheas caused by *Vibrio cholerae*. Several natural products have been identified as blockers of CFTR and/or CaCC including chalcones, xanthenes, flavonoids, piperine, zearalenones and depsidones. Of particular interest piperine has been found to be effective in inhibiting fluid secretion in a mouse model of secretory diarrheas. To promote research translation from drug discovery to new drug development, a mini-gut model has been extensively used to investigate therapeutic potential of experimental intestine-acting drugs. We have demonstrated that selected natural products are effective in exerting the anti-secretory effect in human mini-gut models. Furthermore, since bacterial infection-associated diarrheas are a primary cause of mortality and morbidity in weaning piglets, we have demonstrated that piperine also holds promise as a feed additive for the prevention of weaning-associated diarrheas in a porcine mini-gut model established from the isolated intestinal stem cells. Collectively, efforts from multi-disciplinary researchers are central to the exploration of frontiers in bioscience research with the increasing impact of artificial intelligence being foreseen in the near future.

Keywords: Frontier Research, Drug Discovery, Diarrheas, Translational Research

Acknowledgments: This work was funded by the National Research Council of Thailand (NRCT) and NSRF via the Program Management Unit for Human Resources & Institutional Development, Research and Innovation (grant number B05F650041)

Keynote Session 2

Ecosystem services of bats: Thailand perspective

Sara Bumrungsri

Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla, Thailand.
Corresponding author: sara.b@psu.ac.th

Abstract: There are more than 140 species of bats in Thailand. Fruit bats play role in pollination of several fruit crop and mangrove trees in Thailand, in addition to seed dispersal services. Recent studies indicated that insect-eating bats play major role in insect regulation service especially in farmland and agroforest habitat. A colonial species such as *Mops plicatus* is one among most well-studied species that contribute in pest suppression in paddy field. Several studies confirm that this bat feeds on the most serious rice pest, planthopper, which migrate within the region. Authors also demonstrate that it also feeds on mosquito. Other insect-eating bats are thought to be important pest regulator in different landscape, and more studies are needed. Researchers demonstrate the population decline in both fruit bat and insectivorous bat. These findings raise the conservation concern of bats in Thailand as well as the region, and serious conservation measures should be undertaken both at the local and regional level.

Keywords: : fruit bat, insect-eating bat, pollination, seed dispersal, planthopper

Keynote Session 3

Organic Soil Amendments: Pollution Solution or Environmental Risk

Snežana Maletić^{1,*}, Srđan Rončević¹, Jelena Beljin¹, and Marijana Kragulj Isakovski¹

¹ Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, 21000, Republic of Serbia

* Corresponding author: snezana.maletic@dh.uns.ac.rs

Abstract: Globally valuable resources are continuously lost through waste streams. Therein, carbon-based wastes such as biomass residues and biosolids can emit substantial amounts of greenhouse gases if landfilled or burned off. Thus, strategies to utilize these resources following concepts of circular economy are urgently needed. One promising approach is converting these resources into valuable organic soil amendments (OSA). Application of organics OSA is a widespread practice worldwide expected to grow in use and application scenarios. OSA can play a key role in maintaining soil functioning and facilitating a shift towards a resource-efficient, low-carbon, and climate-resilient agro-economy by minimizing the environmental footprint of agricultural food production. An important aspect of OSA application is that these amendments can be a source and/or a sink of nutrients as well as organic and inorganic pollutants (pharmaceuticals, pesticides, heavy metals etc.). Thus, they are expected to affect soil subsurface and groundwater contamination. Due to the many direct and indirect interactions of organic matter in the complex soil system, numerous processes relevant to nutrient and contaminant dynamics are affected by the application of OSA. Important processes include stabilizing effect for transport, increased solubility of some organic compounds, competition for sorption sites, complexation of metals, and soil organic matter-mineral interactions. Additionally, different OSA are highly variable, with some of them potentially releasing harmful substances. Furthermore, experimental conditions in the lab and field, different soil types, different crops, climate zones, and agricultural management strategies lead to many possible conditions in the soil. This makes a generalizable assessment of OSA effect on sorption, transformation and transport processes in soil challenging. This presentation explores the dual role of organic soil amendments as beneficial soil enhancers and potential environmental risks. Through a review of selected studies, we will highlight the pathways through which these contaminants can enter the soil and their impact on plant health, and soil ecosystems.

Acknowledgments: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. GA No. 101059546-TwinSubDyn.

Keynote Session 4

Sharing Experience with Staff Exchange in Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON)

Surapong Chatpun

Institute of Biomedical Engineering Sciences, Department of Biomedical Sciences and Biomedical Engineering, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, 90110, Thailand

Corresponding author: surapong.c@psu.ac.th

Abstract: International collaboration is very important and gives more opportunity for career development. In my case, I got the opportunity to join the project named “gaitREHub” supported by Horizon Europe Framework Programme (Horizon) in 2023. Horizon Europe is a research and innovation funding programme that tackles many global challenges such as climate change and the UN’s sustainable development goals. It allows the partners from industry and third countries to join and collaborate with this programme. I was involved at the beginning of this project, including drafting the proposal, finding partners and conducting the project. There are many things that I have learnt from this project, including successes and failures. Main issue of this staff exchange is to perform a secondment in European partners’ institutes and do research proposed in the proposal with significant outputs and outcomes. Learning from someone’s experience is one of the effective ways to develop ourselves. Therefore, I will share my experience on the gaitREHub project and tell you how I got it with my European partners.

INVITED SPEAKER

Invited Speaker 1 – Track 1

Traditional use of mints in SE Europe

Bojana Bokić^{1*}, Boris Radak¹, Milica Rat¹ and Goran Anačkov¹

¹ Department of Biology and Ecology, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, 21000, Serbia

* Corresponding author: bojana.bokic@dbe.uns.ac.rs

Abstract:

The genus *Mentha*, a member of the Lamiaceae family, is a large and polymorphic genus native to North America, Europe, Africa, Asia and Australia. The representatives of the genus *Mentha* have been highly valued and cultivated all over the world as a rich source of nonvolatile and volatile metabolites. Their extracts and essential oils show remarkable effects against a wide-range of fungi, bacteria, viruses, insects, hence they are used in control of pathogens and pests, cosmetics, confectionery, culinary, official and traditional medicine to treat various disorders. In this review, a complete survey of the traditional implementation of the genus *Mentha* in SE Europe is reported. The analyses are based on scientific literature obtained from online databases including Google Scholar, PubMed, Scopus and Web of Science, regarding the benefits and traditional main uses of mints in countries of SE Europe, such as Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Greece, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Romania, Serbia and Slovenia.

Keywords: *Mentha*, Lamiaceae, Ethnobotany, Phytotherapy

Acknowledgments: This work was funded by Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Grants no. 451-03-66/2024-03/200125 & 451-03-65/2024-03/200125)

Invited Speaker 2 – Track 2

Beyond Simple Food – Unveiling the Medicinal Benefits and Human Health Risks of Apiaceae Species

Danijela Arsenov^{1,*}, Milan Župunski¹, Nataša Nikolić¹, Milan Borišev¹, Milica Stanković-Popić², Neda Mimica-Dukić³ and Slobodanka Pajević¹

¹ Department of Biology and Ecology, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, 21000, Serbia

² Department of Biology, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Mathematics, University of Pristina, Kosovska Mitrovica, 38220, Serbia

³ Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, 21000, Serbia

* Corresponding author: danijela.arsenov@dbe.uns.ac.rs

Abstract: Parsley, celery, parsnip, and carrot are commonly used in everyday diets as spices and culinary flavorings. Additionally, these plants are recognized for their valuable pharmacological properties and health benefits, classifying them as medicinal herbs and nutraceutical vegetables. Despite the established health benefits of Apiaceae family plants, their chemical composition can vary due to plant species, their varieties, and various external stimuli, including abiotic factors and farming systems. Increasing consumer awareness and concerns about health and environmental issues linked to intensive, industrialized agriculture drive interest in organic farming practices, which aim to provide healthier, more nutritious, higher-quality, and safer food.

To elucidate the influence of farming practices (organic vs conventional) on the chemical composition, antioxidant properties, and health assessment of selected plant species, we screened the content of trace elements (TEs): Mg, Mn, Fe, Ni, Cu, As, Cd, and Pb, activity of antioxidant enzymes, lipid peroxidation, proline and glutathione content, DPPH and FRAP assays, and total phenolic and flavonoid content. As we hypothesized, conventional farming provoked a higher TE accumulation than organic practice, which is observed in the roots of all analyzed species—the exceptions were Cd and Pb, where significant differences did not occur. Further, we quantified the safety of analyzed species based on the hazard index, revealing none or lower health risks associated with the regular consumption of organically grown plants. Farming practices modified the activity of antioxidant enzymes depending on plant species/organs, which is directly related to TEs content. Notably, we observed a higher total phenolic and flavonoid content in the leaves of all tested species grown organically, providing substantial antioxidant activity. Related to that, results pointed out that the methanol extract of parsnip leaves grown organically exhibits the highest antioxidant potential as evidenced by the IC₅₀ values from DPPH and FRAP assays. These findings suggest that future efforts should be directed toward producing plants with a lower potential for toxic element accumulation, thereby enhancing the health benefits of plant foods.

Keywords: Medicinal Plants, Antioxidants, Farming Practice, Hazard Index

Acknowledgments: This work was funded by a project entitled: “Biologically active components and medical potential of functional food grown in Vojvodina Province, Serbia” no. 114-451-2149/2016-03, financed by the Provincial Secretariat for Science and Technological Development, Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Serbia. Also, the authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Grants No. 451-03-66/2024-03/ 200125 & 451-03-65/2024-03/200125).

Invited Speaker 3 – Track 3

From Forest to Pharma: The Potential Effects of Natural Products in Neurological Disorder.

Muhammad Danial Ramli^{1*}, Syntyche Seow², Peggy Cheng²

¹ Faculty of Health and Life Sciences, Management and Science University, Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia

² Ganofarm R&D, 01-01, Skypod Square, Persiaran Puchong Jaya Selatan, Bandar Puchong Jaya, 47100 Puchong, Selangor

* Corresponding author: muhddanial_cheramli@msu.edu.my

Abstract: A progressive loss of neuronal structure and function is a hallmark of neurodegenerative disorders like Alzheimer's disease (AD) and Parkinson's disease (PD), which ultimately lead to abnormalities in cognition and movement. Tremors, bradykinesia, rigidity, and postural instability are among the classic signs of Parkinson's disease. Due to the degeneration of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra, the disease mostly impairs motor function. Parkinson's disease (PD) is characterised by oxidative stress, neuroinflammation, mitochondrial malfunction, and the accumulation of alpha-synuclein protein in Lewy bodies. Cognitive abilities are the primary affected area by Alzheimer's disease, the most common cause of dementia. Alzheimer's disease (AD) is characterised by hyperphosphorylated tau protein-based neurofibrillary tangles and beta-amyloid plaque accumulation. These pathological changes lead to synaptic dysfunction, neuronal death, and brain atrophy, particularly in the hippocampus and cortex. The disease manifests clinically with memory loss, language difficulties, disorientation, and impaired executive functions. Both diseases share common pathogenic mechanisms, including protein aggregation, mitochondrial dysfunction, and neuroinflammation. Genetic factors, such as mutations in the SNCA, LRRK2, and GBA genes in PD, and the APP, PSEN1, and PSEN2 genes in AD, contribute to familial forms of these diseases. Environmental factors also play a significant role in sporadic cases. Presently available treatment approaches mostly provide symptomatic alleviation because neither condition has a known cure. Our products developed through research and development (R&D) including 1) Nevgro Forte®, 2) NeuroVit®, and 3) MyVPro® were created as supplements to aid in the treatment of neurological disorders.

Keywords: Alzheimer's Disease, Parkinson's disease, Neurological Disorder, Movement Disorder

Invited Speaker 4 – Track 4

Tailored Functional Nanomaterials as Peroxidase Mimics on Microfluidic Paper-Based Analytical Devices (μ PADs) for Innovative Point-of-Care Applications

Purim Jarujamrus^{1,2,3}

¹ *Nanomaterials Science, Sensors & Catalysis for Problem-Based Projects, Faculty of Science, Ubon Ratchathani University, Ubon Ratchathani, 34190, Thailand*

² *Department of Chemistry and Center of Excellence for Innovation in Chemistry, Ubon Ratchathani University, Ubon Ratchathani, 34190, Thailand*

³ *Department of Applied Chemistry, Faculty of Science and Technology, Keio University, 3-14-1 Hiyoshi, Kohoku-ku, Yokohama 223-8522, Japan*

Corresponding author: purim.j@ubu.ac.th

Abstract: Our group has developed functional nanomaterials, such as nitrogen-doped carbon dots (N-CDs) and vanadium-doped porous cobalt oxide (V-porous Co_3O_4), as peroxidase mimics for point-of-care applications integrated into microfluidic paper-based analytical devices (μ PADs). In the first study, N-CDs were synthesized via a hydrothermal method and characterized thoroughly. These N-CDs served as peroxidase mimics for colorimetric total cholesterol (TC) analysis on 3D- μ PADs, enabling semiquantitative TC detection in whole blood within 10 minutes, providing a low-cost, rapid, and sensitive alternative ¹. In the second study, V-porous Co_3O_4 was synthesized as a superior peroxidase mimic for glucose and TC assessment in whole blood on a 2D- μ PAD. Created using wax screen printing and cutting, this device allows simultaneous analysis of glucose and TC in 5 minutes with a 15 μL blood drop. The catalytic activity of V-porous Co_3O_4 oxidized H_2O_2 , producing color indicators for glucose and TC levels. This 2D- μ PAD offers a rapid, cost-effective solution for point-of-care blood biomarker detection ². The third application involves a fluorometric aptasensor for low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) detection using aptamer-enhanced peroxidase activity of gold nanoparticles (AuNPs). Functionalizing AuNPs with an LDL-C-specific thiolated-aptamer increased their catalytic efficiency, oxidizing OPD by H_2O_2 into a fluorescent product. The aptasensor exhibited a linear relationship between signal intensity and LDL-C concentration in the range of 0.05–1 mg dL^{-1} , with a detection limit of 0.0230 mg dL^{-1} , correlating well with clinical methods ³. In summary, these cost-effective devices enable rapid, on-site monitoring of real samples. They offer low cost, easy fabrication, and scalability for mass production. They represent innovative, environmentally friendly, and affordable detection technologies with anticipated analytes.

Reference(s)

1. Kitchawengkul, N.; Prakobkij, A.; Anutrasakda, W.; Yodsin, N.; Jungsuttiwong, S.; Chunta, S.; Amatongchai, M.; and Jarujamrus, P. *Anal. Chem.* **2021**, 93 (18), 6989-6999.
2. Wongsing, B.; Prakobkij, A.; Anutrasakda, W.; Jarujamrus, P. *Anal. Chem.* **2022**, 94, 13785-13794.
3. Prakobkij, A.; Saenmuangchin, R.; Chunta, S.; Amatongchai, M.; Citterio, D.; Jarujamrus, P. *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.*, **2024**, 7, 12356-12365.

Purim Jarujamrus is an Associate Professor at the Department of Chemistry, Ubon Ratchathani University, Thailand. He received his Ph.D. in Analytical Chemistry from Mahidol University, Thailand, in 2012. Since 2024, he has served as the National Representative (NR) of Thailand in the Analytical Chemistry Division of IUPAC. His research focuses on the development of functional nanomaterials for fiber-based microfluidic analytical devices for innovative chemical and biosensing applications. To date, he has published approximately 80 articles in peer-reviewed journals.

Invited Speaker – Session 5

Horizon Europe Funding Opportunities: Guidelines for Application

Gordana Vlahović

International Relations & Project Office, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, 21000, Republic of Serbia
Corresponding author: gordanav@uns.ac.rs

Abstract: Find your way through the ongoing EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon Europe – learn where and how to identify the right call, find partners, gain international visibility and recognition, and make your research more globally impactful.

Invited Speaker – Session 6

Erasmus+ Capacity Building in Higher Education (CBHE): opportunities for universities and staff

Khobkhul Inieam

Delegation of the European Union to Thailand, Bangkok 10330, Thailand
Corresponding author: khobkhul.inieam@eeas.europa.eu

Abstract: Erasmus+ is the European Union (EU) programme for education, training, youth and sport for the period 2021-27. Erasmus+ funds academic mobility and cooperation projects that involve partners from 27 EU Member States and 6 associated countries on the one hand, and from non-associated countries throughout the world on the other. Erasmus+ supports activities that are closely matched with the common priorities for cooperation policy with third countries and regions.

Erasmus+ Capacity Building in Higher Education action (CBHE) projects, which last from two to three years, are aimed at modernising and reforming higher education institutions, developing new curricula, improving governance, and building relationships between higher education and enterprises. They can also tackle policy topics and issues, preparing the ground for higher education reform, in cooperation with national authorities. CBHE is a funding for higher institution/universities to build capacity of its staff/students. It is neither a grant for individual nor a research grant. Around 20% of the annual global budget for CBHE projects is earmarked for Asian countries. The first selection of projects in the 2021-27 phase was made in 2022.

Invited Speaker – Session 7

Erasmus+ Projects: How to Get Involved? Navigating the Erasmus+ KA1 Mobility Program

Ivana Pejović

International Relations Office, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, 21000, Serbia
Corresponding author: ivana.pejovic@pmf.uns.ac.rs

Abstract: Drawing from nearly a decade of experience at the Faculty of Sciences at the University of Novi Sad (UNS) in Serbia, this presentation offers practical insights into engaging with Erasmus+ projects, particularly the KA1 mobility program. Serbia's journey from being a partner country to becoming a program country (or a third country fully associated with the Erasmus+ framework) has created numerous opportunities for student and staff exchanges at UNS.

This presentation showcases real-life scenarios and success stories, demonstrating the program's ability to enhance international cooperation, academic exchange, and cultural understanding. These stories highlight how participation in Erasmus+ has enriched our institution, provided invaluable experiences for our students and staff, and strengthened our ties with international partners. It also addresses common challenges, such as coordination and administrative hurdles, and shares strategies for overcoming them.

Additionally, Thailand's status as a partner country in Erasmus+ is discussed, highlighting successful Thai-Serbia partnerships and projects. This comparative perspective underscores the benefits and opportunities available to both partner and program countries.

The lessons learned from these experiences provide valuable insights for other institutions seeking to maximize their participation in the Erasmus+ KA1 mobility program. This presentation offers a comprehensive overview of the transformative power of Erasmus+ and provides attendees with actionable strategies to enhance their international mobility initiatives.

Keywords: Erasmus+ KA1 Mobility, International Cooperation, Student and Staff Exchange, Lessons Learned, Serbia

BSC Building

Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University

ORAL PRESENTATION

ORAL PRESENTATION

Track 1

Biology,

Environment and Climate Change

Track 2

Biotechnology,

Biochemistry and Functional Food

Track 3

Bioactive

Natural Products and Biomedicine

Track 4

Bio-sensing

Technology and Data Science

Oral Presentation - OR1-01

Pilot study on the use of two different environmental pollution bioindicators, moss and bee, in an area with a high cancer incidence

Viviana Maresca^{1,†}, Nunzio Antonio Cacciola², Marcello Scivicco², Piergiorgio Cianciullo³, Alessia Postiglione³, Andrea Ariano², Iris Maria Forte⁴, Luigi Alfano⁴, Carmelina Antonella Iannuzzi⁴, Riccardo Fedeli⁵, Stefano Loppi⁵, Sergio Sorbo⁶, Antonio Giordano^{7,8}, Lorella Severino^{2†}, Adriana Basile^{3†}

¹ Department of Life Sciences, Health and Health Professions, University of Rome "link Campus", Rome, 00165, Italy

² Department of Veterinary Medicine and Animal Production, Division of Toxicology, University of Naples Federico II, Naples, 80125, Italy

³ Department of Biology, University of Naples "Federico II", Naples, 80125, Italy

⁴ Department of Breast and Thoracic Oncology, Istituto Nazionale Tumori, IRCCS, Fondazione G. Pascale, Naples, 80131, Italy

⁵ Department of Life Sciences, University of Siena, Siena 53100, Italy

⁶ CeSMA, section of Microscopy, University of Naples Federico II, Naples, 80125, Italy

⁷ Sbarro Health Research Organization, Temple University, Philadelphia, PA 19122, Pennsylvania, USA

⁸ Department of Medical Biotechnologies, University of Siena, Siena, 53100, Italy

[†] These authors contributed equally to this work.

* Corresponding author: v.maresca@unilink.it

Abstract:

In this pilot study, we investigated of atmospheric potentially toxic elements (PTEs) levels at two areas of S Italy, subjected to different human impact, using two different biomonitors: the moss *Scorpiurum circinatum* and the honeybee *Apis mellifera*. The moss was placed near apiaries in two locations: in a very natural place, the forest of Palazzo Reale Carditello, and in a location with high industrial and anthropogenic pollution the outskirts of Giugliano. These two sites are located near the sadly known "Land of Fires", characterized by the illegal burning of waste, including toxic ones. In addition, it was selected two places far from any possible pollution and considered them as the control sites, Monte Faito for moss and Vico Equense for bees. *S. circinatum* bags were exposed for 21, 42, and 63 days, while the honeybees were sampled on the 63rd day along with the last set of moss bags. All samples were used to analyze and identify the possible bioaccumulation of PTEs. Regarding bioaccumulation in the control sites, the absence of PTEs pollution has been confirmed. Surprisingly, comparable pollution levels were observed in the two sites characterized by different environmental conditions. This result was confirmed by both bioindicators. Our results, showed that moss has a greater bioaccumulation capacity between the two, so we focused on it for further analysis. Ultrastructural observations, levels of ROS, and antioxidant enzyme activity were considered. Both the ultrastructural observations and the oxidative stress data show the absence of alterations in the samples exposed in the control site while between the two sites the alterations observed do not show significant differences, confirming the data on bioaccumulation. Our results

demonstrate that the contribution to the presence of PTEs in the air is mainly given by toxic fumes while that due to the degree of anthropization is negligible.

Keywords: Bioindicators; *Scorpiurum circinatum*; *Apis mellifera*; Heavy metals; Air environmental pollution; Land of fires

Oral Presentation - OR1-02

From student exchange to climate change

Milica Stankovic^{1,2*}

¹ Excellence Center for Biodiversity of Peninsular Thailand, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla 90112, Thailand

² Field Marine Station, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla 90112, Thailand

* Corresponding author: milica.s@psu.ac.th

Abstract:

This presentation explores my personal journey from a student at University Novi Sad (UNS) to a researcher at Prince of Songkla University (PSU), demonstrating how student exchange programs can significantly shape our approach to global environmental issues. During my undergraduate studies at Novi Sad University, I developed a keen interest in environmental science. The opportunity to study at PSU as an exchange student marked an important moment in my career, exposing me to a diverse academic environment and pioneering re-search in coastal ecosystems and climate change. At PSU, I became particularly interested in blue carbon—the carbon captured and stored by coastal ecosystems, such as mangroves, salt marshes, and seagrasses. and their potential to mitigate the effects of climate change. As part of a dynamic research team and vast opportunities provided by the university, I focused on quantifying these ecosystems, the services they provide, their significant contribution and potential to mitigate the impacts on climate change nationally and regionally. The outcomes of the past and current research contribute towards national policies and shape global frameworks on climate change.

This journey from exchange student to global expert in blue carbon illustrates the profound impact of international academic collaborations on personal and professional development. It demonstrates how student exchange programs can inspire individuals to engage in addressing critical global challenges. Through this journey, I have been able to contribute to the broader understanding of coastal ecosystems, address the current knowledge gaps and influence policy frameworks on a national and international level. The significance of the exchange program provided by UNS and PSU lies in cultivating the next generation of environmental leaders and their role in fostering innovative approaches of global issues such as climate change.

Keywords: Student exchange, Blue carbon, Coastal ecosystems, Climate change

Oral Presentation - OR1-03

The quality of sea grape growth in culture pond related to the seasonal change

Sirinya Sirimahawan¹, Eknarin Rodcharoen² and Bongkot Wichachucherd^{1*}

¹ Department of Science and Bioinnovation, Faculty of Liberal Arts and Science, Kasetsart University, Kamphaeng Saen, Nakhon Pathom 73140. Thailand.

² Aquatic Science and Innovative Management Division, Faculty of Natural Resources; and Discipline of Excellence for Sustainable Aquaculture, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla 90110. Thailand.

*Corresponding author: bongkot.w@ku.th

Abstract

Sea grape is a well – known in rich nutrient and antioxidant seaweed, so it become to functional natural food at present. In Thailand, the farmers had economical culture along the coastline underneath Thai government promotion such as Phetchaburi province. An open seaweed culture pond was popular in this areas, similar to salt pond which had circulation system by seawater diversion from nearby coast. This research was hypothesized that environmental factors changing could affect to quality of sea grape such as the growth pattern, morphology and color, inconsistent throughout the year. This study aimed to perceive about the quality of sea grape in open ponds at Phetchaburi province in year – round comparing two pond stations. Air and water temperature, salinity, pH, total dissolve solid dissolved oxygen and rainfall data was record through a year. Morphological data, yield and percentage of green color were examined for the quality from the fresh sea grape between two stations. ANOVA and CCA was used for statistical analysis. The results showed that the water temperature and salinity were important environmental factors affecting to sea grape quality. There were two pattern of growth- Guerrilla growth which exhibited long stolon and low density more than Phalanx growth showing high density. Spatial and temporal variation were found in this study. Moreover, the culture system maintenance was the other cause which could affect to the sea grape quality. Thus, the knowledges obtained from this study can be used as the sea grape cultivating guidelines for farmers to get the high quality sea grape and for worthwhile investment in valuable seaweed marketing. Besides sea grape, this study can be applied for other seaweed in same habitat characteristic.

Keywords: Sea grape, Environmental factor, Quality, Growth, Season

Acknowledgments: This work was funded by Kasetsart University Research and Development Institute KURDI (grant number FF65(KU)15.65).

Oral Presentation - OR1-04

CYTOGENETICS AND GENOME SIZE ESTIMATION OF THE NARROW-LIP SPATHOGLOTTIS *AUREA* LINDL. (ORCHIDACEAE) FROM PENINSULAR MALAYSIA

Umi Natra Shaharudin^{1*}, Farah Alia Nordin¹, Ahmad Sofiman Othman¹, and Mohd Razik Midin²

¹ School of Biological Sciences, Universiti Sains Malaysia, Pulau Pinang, 11800, Malaysia

² Kulliyah of Science, International Islamic University Malaysia, Kuantan Campus, Pahang, 25200, Malaysia

* Corresponding author: uminatra98@gmail.com

Abstract:

Spathoglottis aurea Lindl. is the yellow-flowered terrestrial orchids from genus *Spathoglottis* Blume which is native to Peninsular Malaysia. This species is one of the two species under this genus represented by very narrow, needle-like labellum (a modified petal unique to family Orchidaceae). Another species that is almost identical in morphology with *S. aurea* is *S. microchilina* Kraenzl. Due to their high similarities in vegetative and floral characteristics across populations, confusion in species identification and taxonomic placement of *S. aurea* and *S. microchilina* have long been reported by several authors. Previously, several studies using comparative morphological assessment and molecular markers have been carried out to delimit these two species as separate taxa or just a highly variable form of *S. aurea*. However, discreet examination on the chromosome characteristics supported by genome size estimation of these two highly confused is another powerful approach to further clarify the taxonomic boundary of *S. aurea* and *S. microchilina*. Thus, the aims of this study are, i) to characterize the chromosomes of *S. aurea* via cytogenetic techniques. The characters of the chromosome that will be studied include the number, shape, size and karyotypes. Through cytogenetic analysis, the differences in the content of chromosomes may reveal differences in the genetic content of a species. The number, size, shape and karyotypes of chromosome are always fixed, thus chromosome characterization is highly reliable for species identification. ii) to utilize genome size estimation via flow cytometry to estimate the genetic content of the species. Taxonomic placement of these two species will be further supported using cytogenetic analysis, thus resolving complexity surrounding this *S. aurea* and *S. microchilina*.

Keywords: [Orchidaceae; Chromosome Count; Flow Cytometry; Cytotaxonomy; Genome Size]

Acknowledgments: Dr. Farah Alia Nordin, School of Biological Sciences, Universiti Sains Malaysia

Oral Presentation - OR1-05

SURVIVAL STRATEGIES OF EPIPHYTIC AND LITHOPHYTIC ORCHIDS: EXPLORING THEIR ECOLOGICAL PARTNERSHIP WITH LICHENS IN DIVERSE ECOSYSTEMS

Siti Nadia Mohd Nizam^{1*} and Farah Alia Nordin¹

¹ School of Biological Sciences, Universiti Sains Malaysia, 11800, Penang, Malaysia

* Corresponding author: nadianizam25@student.usm.my

Orchids are classified into two growth habits which are epiphytic and terrestrial. This study highlights epiphytic, and its subgroup lithophytic, orchids. Lithophytic orchids are orchids that have adapted to grow on rocky surfaces rather than on trees. The orchids have specialized adaptation, such as aerial roots and velamen, in order to sustain their survivability by absorbing moisture and nutrients from its surrounding. Studies have reported symbiotic relationships of orchids with mycorrhizal fungi to aid in nutrient uptake. Interestingly, epiphytic and lithophytic orchids are often found together with lichen on tree or on rocks. The relationship between epiphytic and lithophytic orchid with lichen is still understudied in Malaysia although it shows potential role as microbial partner to orchids. Hence, through anatomical study on selected species of orchids, valuable information on ecological interaction between lichens and the studied orchids can be proven with the presence of pelotons and raphides in the isolated root cell. The study are done at three different geological ecosystem which are hill forest, montane forest and limestone forest in northern part of Peninsular Malaysia. Significant observations were recorded with different species of lichen accomodating different, sometimes similar, species of orchids. These results galvanises the concept of obligate symbiosis adapted by orchids with mycorrhizal fungi in order to increase its survivability.

Keywords: Orchids, Lithophytes, Lichen, Symbiosis, Anatomy

Acknowledgments: This work was funded by the National Conservation Trust Fund for Natural Resources by Ministry of Natural Resources, Environment and Climate Change Malay

Oral Presentation - OR1-06

[Morphometric analysis of *Spathoglottis plicata* and *Spathoglottis plicata* var. *alba*]

Farhan Rashid^{1,*}, Farah Alia Nordin¹, Ahmad Sofiman Othman¹ and Mohd Razik Midin²

¹ School of Biological Sciences, Universiti Sains Malaysia, 11800, Penang, Malaysia

² Kulliyah of Science, International Islamic University Malaysia, 25200, Kuantan, Pahang, Malaysia

* Corresponding author: farhanrashids@student.usm.my

Abstract:

Spathoglottis plicata Blume (family Orchidaceae) is a terrestrial orchid species expressing complex plasticity in terms of morphological forms, particularly flower colour. It is reported to be ranging from deep mauve to pink and white, with the white form currently recognised as a variety or forma. However, recent finding highlighted some new insight suggesting that the white variety of *Spathoglottis plicata* can be elevated into species level. Following that, we investigated *Spathoglottis plicata* var. *alba* under morphometric analysis to elucidate this possibility. We constructed a phylogenetic tree using the Mesquite software utilising selected morphological characters. Maximum Parsimony analysis showed that *Spathoglottis plicata* var. *alba* observed does not fall within the purple *Spathoglottis plicata* clade. This finding is also supported by molecular phylogenetic analysis published prior to this study. We suggest that the white variety should be elevated to species level, even more with future supporting data from anatomical and cytological analysis.

Keywords: Orchidaceae, *Spathoglottis*, Morphology

Acknowledgments: This work is funded by the National Conservation Trust Fund for Natural Resources by Ministry of Natural Resources, Environment and Climate Change Malaysia.

Oral Presentation - OR1-08

Recycling fish scale waste into high value-added products

Kwansuda Kongthong^{1,2}, Natthika Sinupakarn¹, and Kaewta Kaewtatip^{1,2,*}

¹ Division of Physical Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla, 90110, Thailand

² Center of Excellence for Trace Analysis and Biosensor, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla, 90110, Thailand

* Corresponding author: [kaewta.k@psu.ac.th]

Abstract:

Waste from seafood processing is a rich source of calcium carbonate and other organic components such as proteins, polysaccharides and chitin. Fish scale contain valuable organic components that include collagen, proteins, lipids, and polysaccharides. The inorganic components of fish scale can be used as precursors in the production of hydroxyapatite (HAp). HAp is an interesting nontoxic, low-density, nonimmunogenic, biocompatible material that exhibits antioxidant activity. To our knowledge, there are few reported applications of HAp as a filler for starch-based bioplastics. Therefore, we presented a potential application of HAp extracted from seafood waste as a filler in a biodegradable starch foam and film.

Keywords: [Waste, fish scale, hydroxyapatite, starch, bioplastic]

Acknowledgments:

This work was funded by National Research Council of Thailand (NRCT): (Contact No N41A661161) and the Faculty of Science and Prince of Songkla University, Thailand We thank Siam Modified Starch Co., Ltd. for the donation of cassava starch. We also thank Mr. Thomas Duncan Coyne for assistance with the English text.

Oral Presentation - OR1-09

Impacts of fish cage farming on underlying sediments and macrofauna of Songkhla Lake, Southern Thailand

Pervin, R., Hayewachi, L., Sinso, T. and Wangkulangkul, K*

* *Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla, Thailand*
Corresponding author: kringpaka.w@psu.ac.th

Abstract: Songkhla Lake is the southernmost part of a tropical estuarine Songkhla lagoon system, located in southern Thailand. The area is rich in aquatic biodiversity and there has reportedly been an increase in fishing, aquaculture, and other human intervention in this significant water body. Among these, seabass aquaculture is one of the predominant activities. Fish cage farms are evident throughout the lake but the impacts of the farming on the environment are not well understood. The present study aims to investigate the impact of fish cage culture on underlying sediment and abundance of benthic community in Songkhla Lake. The samples will be collected in the middle of August 2024 at three areas influenced by cage culture activities including Ko Yo, Ta-rai and Ta-sao. At each area, samples will be collected at stations along three line transect with three levels of distances from the cages: at 0 m, 10 m and 100 m. At each station water quality parameter such as temperature, salinity, DO and pH will be measured during the sampling. Sediment sample will be collected from each station using a grab and later will be analyzed for organic matter, particle size, total nitrogen and phosphorus. Three replicated samples of macrofauna will be collected using an Ekman grab with a catch area of 0.025 m². All materials retained in the grab will be sieved through a 0.5 mm mesh and the fauna will be brought to the laboratory for further identification. Macroinvertebrates from all samples will be identified to species level or to the lowest taxonomic level. We hypothesize that all parameters will exhibit difference between distances from the cage especially high load of organic matters is expected to be found near the fish cages as food excess from fish feeding may be re-leased into the water and deposited in sediments. This study is expected to provide new in-sights into the impacts that current aquaculture operations are having on the aquatic environment associated with Songkhla Lake. It will also assist in gathering the information required for sustainable management of this valuable natural resource.

Keywords: Songkhla Lake, Cage culture, Sediment, Benthic community

Acknowledgments: This work is self-funded by Kringpaka Wangkulangkul.

Oral Presentation - OR1-10

Heavy metal concentration in seaweed and seagrasses from the Andaman coastal areas: A case study from Lidee Island and Libong Island

Sinjai Phetcharat¹, Nantaporn Noosai², and Jaruwat Mayakun^{1*}

¹ Molecular Evolution and Computational Biology Research Unit, Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla, Thailand

² Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla, Thailand

* Corresponding author: jaruwat.may@psu.ac.th

Abstract: Heavy metals were investigated in seaweed, *Halimeda macroloba* and seagrasses, *Halophila ovalis*, *Thalassia hemprichii*, and *Cymodocea rotundata*, from Lidee Island, Satun province and Libong Island, Trang province. Heavy metal concentration in ambient seawater and surface sediment were also determined in each area. Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES) technique was used to analyze for the heavy metal concentration. The concentrations in all sample and sediment were used to analyze bioconcentration factor (BCF) that indicate the ratio of heavy metal concentration in each species and the underlying sediment. This study revealed 8 elements that ordered to Mn>Zn>Cu>As>Cr>Ni>Pb>Cd in all species excepting *H. macroloba* was not found Pb. Cd was only not detected in sediment while Mn and Ni was only not detected in seawater of both areas. All species of seagrasses has higher concentration level of each metal than in seaweed. This result might be because seagrasses have more complex root and stem system while our seaweed accumulate a lot of CaCO₃ that might disrupt the metal ions absorbance. When comparing between the locations, Libong Island has higher concentration and more variety of heavy metals than in Lidee Island. Our result suggested that Lidee Island seems to be pristine area because this area is protected under natural park while Libong Island is tourist hotpot and near mouth river. The BCFs indicate that all seagrass species from Libong Island can accumulated Cd in highest proportion. This result is suggested the utility of seagrass as bioindicators of Cd which might be disturbed by human activities. This study was the first study of heavy metal content in the seaweed and seagrasses in these two areas. The accumulation of heavy metals in biota and environment can be the hazard implication and reference values for the further measurement.

Keywords: [Trace element, Human disturbance, Seaweed, Seagrass, Biological index]

Acknowledgments: [This research was supported by the National Science, Research and Innovation Fund (NSRF) and Prince of Songkla University (Grant No. SCI6701250S).]

Oral Presentation - OR1-11

A New Species of *Hipposideros* from Southeast Asia: Integrative Taxonomic Approach Reveals Cryptic Diversity

Phutita Wongwaiyut¹, and Pipat Soisook^{2,*}

¹ Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla, Thailand, 90110

² Princess Maha Chakri Sirindhorn Natural History Museum, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla, Thailand, 90110

* Corresponding author, Email: phutita9201@gmail.com

Abstract: The taxonomic identity of the *Hipposideros cineraceus* complex in the Thai-Malay Peninsula has been a longstanding issue due to morphological variation among species in the *Hipposideros bicolor* species group. This study presents a comprehensive investigation of this complex, elucidates taxonomic identity of each taxon and describes a new species, *Hipposideros kingstonae* sp. nov., based on specimens from Thailand and Malaysia. The new species is distinguished by its unique external, craniodental, and bacular morphology, as well as echolocation call frequency, defining it uniquely from other *Hipposideros* species in the region. Phylogenetic analyses based on mitochondrial DNA places *H. kingstonae* as a sister clade to *H. kunzi* and *H. bicolor*. In addition, this research also documents the first record of *H. einnaythu* in Thailand, expanding its known geographic range. Our study underscores the significance of integrating morphological, genetic, and acoustic data to address taxonomic challenges and enhance our understanding of bat biodiversity in Southeast Asia.

Keywords: Chiroptera, Hipposideridae, new species, phylogeny

Acknowledgments: We would like to thank the Department of National Park, Wildlife and Plant Conservation, Thailand, and the Department of Wildlife and National Parks Peninsular Malaysia (DWNP), Malaysia Economic Planning Unit (UPE: 40/200/19/2781) for the research permits to Pipat Soisook and Juliana Senawi, respectively. We give special thanks to the staff of Halabala Wildlife Research Station for their support and collaboration. We are indebted to Wieslaw Bogdanowicz for his support of the molecular work at the beginning of the study. At PSU, we thank the director, Chutamas Satasook, and staff of Princess Maha Chakri Sirindhorn Natural History Museum, as well as the staff of the Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University. We thank Sai Sein Lin Oo, Zin Mar Myo, Moe Moe Aung of the Department of Zoology, University of Mandalay, Khin Swe Oo of Myeik University, and Aung Lin and staff of Fauna & Flora International (FFI)—Myanmar Programme, for their help with fieldwork and specimens. We are grateful to Ibnu Maryanto of the Indonesian Institute of Science (LIPI) and Roberto Portela-Miguez of the Natural History Museum, London, UK, and Tshering Dendup from Bhutan, for their permission to examine specimens and share the data. We would like to thank Pachara Promnopwong, Najthamas Mekmuang, Awatsaya Pimsai, Abdulloh Samoh, and Sakiya Morlor for their help in field and laboratory work. Bat research in Krau Wildlife Reserve, Malaysia was supported by National Science Foundation (NSF) USA through Boston University and Texas Tech University. JS was supported by National Science Fund - USA through Texas Tech University (ST-2019-006) and Malaysia Ministry of Higher Education (FRGS/1/2020/WAB11/UKM/02/3). FAAK thank the Economic Planning Unit of the Malaysian Prime Minister's Department (UPE: 40/200/19/1466), Department of Wildlife and National Parks (JPHL&TN(IP):60-4/1.13 Jld 4 (64)), Universiti Malaysia Sarawak, Sarawak Forestry Corporation, Sarawak Forestry Department (NPW.907.4.2-112), and Sabah Parks (TS/PTD/5/4 Jld. 24 (76)) for permission to conduct wildlife research in Malaysia. FAAK was supported by the Malaysian Ministry of Higher Education (FRGS/1/2019/ WAB13/UNIMAS/03/2). PW thanks the Development and Promotion of Science and Technology Talents Project (DPST) for their financial support. The bat research of PS was supported by Thailand Research Fund (TRF), grant number DBG6180028, and the Plant Genetic Conservation Project under the initiative of Her Royal Highness Princess Maha Chakri Sirindhorn (RSPG), grant numbers SCI6401002 and SCI600089S.

Oral Presentation - OR1-12

Increase in leaf greenness is an adaptative strategy of rice to P deficiency

Pattanapong Jaisue^{1,2,*}, Sompop Pinit³ and Lompong Klinnawee^{1,2}

¹ *Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University*

² *Plant Cell and Physiology for Sustainable Agriculture Research Unit, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University*

³ *Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Medical Science, Naresuan University*

* Corresponding author: pattanapong.jsue@gmail.com

Abstract: Rice enhances leaf greenness in response to P deficiency. This increase in leaf greenness in P-deficient rice seedlings correlates with higher chlorophyll content. However, it remains unclear whether the increase in leaf greenness is specifically induced by P deficiency or by other abiotic stresses. In this study, KDML105 rice seedlings were cultured in Hoagland's solution and treated with gradual levels of P availability, salinity, and copper for two weeks. The results showed that young rice seedling leaves increased greenness through the accumulation of chlorophyll A and B in response to P deficiency, whereas chlorophyll contents were not increased in response to the other stresses. However, the greener leaves of P-deficient rice seedlings failed to maintain the efficiency of photosystem II photochemistry. These findings may shed light on monitoring P deficiency in rice through leaf color, which is essential for improving fertilizer management in precision agriculture.

Keywords: phosphorus, KDML105 rice, leaf greenness and photosynthetic pigments

ORAL PRESENTATION

Track 1

Biology,

Environment and Climate Change

Track 2

Biotechnology,

Biochemistry and Functional Food

Track 3

Bioactive

Natural Products and Biomedicine

Track 4

Bio-sensing

Technology and Data Science

Oral Presentation - OR2-01

Green solutions for recovery of secondary metabolites compounds

Nemanja Teslić^{1,*}, Aleksandra Mišan¹, Milica Pojić^{1,2}, Alena Stupar¹, Branimir Pavlić² and Anamarija Mandić¹

¹ Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, 21000, Serbia

² Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, 21000, Serbia

* Corresponding author: nemanja.teslic@fins.uns.ac.rs

Abstract: The human population is on a constant increase which results in rising demand for health-beneficial bioactive compounds (BACs) and in conjunction with climate change and natural resources scarcity poses serious challenges to the food, cosmetic and/or pharmaceutical industry. These challenges could be effectively tackled via two major pathways: (i) reduction of BACs loss; (ii) development and application of more sustainable technologies. The agri-food industry discards a vast amount of waste and by-products during food processing. Also, natural resources such as medicinal and aromatic plants are not fully valorized by modern industry. If all these materials are not treated properly, such a large quantity of biological waste could pose a serious threat to the environment and human health. However, these natural resources are considered as the source of valuable BACs (e.g. polyphenols, phytosterols, terpenes, carotenoids, etc.) with promising potential for further exploitation. Thus, if a part of this material is valorized and reused effectively, this could be an opportunity for further development of the sustainable food, cosmetic and pharmaceutical industry and a clear pathway to reduce loss of BACs.

The recovery of BACs from plant matrices involves the utilization of some kind of solvent. The conventional extraction techniques have certain limitations such as using organic solvents harmful to human health and the environment, decreased extract quality due to solvents residuals in the final product and increased energy demand. To overcome these limitations we are urged to develop innovative and eco-friendly solutions to fully exploit biological waste for the next generation of products. One of the potential green solutions may be the utilization of natural deep eutectic solvents (NADES) composed only of edible, recyclable, non-toxic compounds that are present in nature. More precisely, organic acids, water, sugars, fatty acids, amino acids, terpenes, alcohols, and other compounds some of which can be mixed in a certain ratio to create tailor-made solvents suitable for a wide range of applications. Thus, NADES application in extraction technologies seems to be a viable tool for upgrading existing processes.

Keywords: Green extraction processes, NADES, valorization, bioactives

Acknowledgments: This work was funded by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and 599 Innovation, Republic of Serbia (Contract No. 451-03-66/2024-03/200222).

Oral Presentation - OR2-02

Genomic Characterization and Phylogenetic Analysis of *Enterocloster aldenensis* PSU25A: An Opportunistic Pathogen in Southern Thailand

Thunchanok Yaikhan¹, Mingkwan Yingkajorn², Nattarika Chaichana^{1,4}, Nonthawat Thepsimanon², Sirikan Suwannasin¹, Ei Phway Thant¹, Kamonnut Singkhamanan¹, Sarunyou Chusri³, Rattanaruji Pomwised⁴, Monwadee Wonglapsuwan⁴ and Komwit Surachat^{1,5,*}

¹ Department of Biomedical Sciences and Biomedical Engineering, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

² Department of Pathology, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

³ Division of Infectious Diseases, Department of Internal Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

⁴ Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

⁵ Translational Medicine Research Center, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

* Correspondence: komwit.s@psu.ac.th

Abstract:

Enterocloster aldenensis is an anaerobic, Gram-positive bacterium commonly found in the human gut, where it helps ferment complex carbohydrates. However, it can also act as an opportunistic pathogen in clinical settings. In this study, we present the genomic characterization of an *E. aldenensis* strain PSU25A that was initially misidentified as *Bacteroides* spp. during routine identification at Songklanagarind Hospital, Thailand. Whole-genome sequencing (WGS) revealed the presence of the *tet(M)* gene, which confers resistance to tetracyclines. Additionally, we identified mobile genetic elements (MGEs), such as plasmids and integrative conjugative elements, which may facilitate horizontal gene transfer.

Virulence factor analysis identified multiple genes related to pathogenicity, including those involved in the Type VI Secretion System (T6SS), pili biogenesis, toxin transport, and stress response, suggesting a capacity for host cell interaction and adaptation to various environments. Functional annotation showed a diverse metabolic profile, with numerous genes associated with carbohydrate and amino acid metabolism, as well as stress response, indicating an ability to adapt to changing conditions. Further analysis using antiSMASH identified a ranthipeptide biosynthetic gene cluster, suggesting potential for producing bioactive compounds.

Phylogenetic analysis showed that *E. aldenensis* PSU25A clustered in the same clade as *E. aldenensis* AM40-2AC, an isolate from human feces in China, suggesting possible transmission between different geographical regions. These findings improve our understanding of the genomic characteristics of *E. aldenensis* PSU25A, including its resistance mechanisms and its potential role

as an emerging opportunistic pathogen. This study highlights the need for further research to clarify the clinical significance and epidemiology of this species.

Keywords: Whole Genome Sequencing, *Enterocloster aldenensis*, Antibiotic Resistance Gene, Mobile Genetic Elements, Phylogenetic Analysis

Acknowledgments: This work was funded by the NSRF through the Program Management Unit for Human Resources & Institutional Development, Research, and Innovation, under grant numbers B13F660074 and B13F670076. Additionally, this research was provided by the Postdoctoral Fellowship from Prince of Songkla University, Thailand.

Oral Presentation - OR2-03

Colorimetric recombinase polymerase amplification for rapid detection of *Staphylococcus pseudintermedius*

Pavarish Jantorn^{1,2}, Aekkaraj Nualla-ong¹, and Dennapa Saeloh Sotthibandhu^{2,*}

¹ Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla, Thailand

² Faculty of Medical Technology, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla, Thailand

* Corresponding author: dennapa.sa@psu.ac.th

Abstract: *Staphylococcus pseudintermedius* is known for its pathogenic potential in canine infections such as pyoderma, otitis externa, respiratory tract infections, and keratitis. Generally, the detection of staphylococci takes 3–5 days including drug susceptibility testing. However, *S. pseudintermedius* can be misidentified for *Staphylococcus aureus* using the phenotypic method and rapid biochemical kit because of similar characteristics such as coagulase enzyme production. This could lead to the failure of the treatment. Recombinase polymerase amplification (RPA) is a promising solution because it improves amplification specificity and requires only one pair-specific primer. The amplification can be done within 20–30 minutes in a temperature range of 37–42 °C. These make RPA more convenient for pathogen detection in clinical use. Here, we developed a rapid assay for the identification of *S. pseudintermedius* based on RPA. The primers were designed from the *spsL* gene without any cross-amplification to other species. The method was carried on crude DNA extracted by boiling assay and performed within 20 minutes at 37 °C. The amplification product was visualized by color change seen with hydroxynaphthol blue (HNB). The specificity of the detection was high with no cross-reaction. The rapid detection developed in this study is a stable, simple, and rapid step to diagnose *S. pseudintermedius* infections for proper treatment.

Keywords: [Recombinase polymerase amplification, *Staphylococcus pseudintermedius*, Rapid detection, RPA]

Acknowledgments: [This research study was supported by the National Science, Research and Innovation Fund (NSRF), Prince of Songkla University [Grant No. MET6601334S], and the Graduate School, Prince of Songkla University [Grant No. PSU_PHD2564-02].]

Oral Presentation - OR2-04

Thorough Screening of Potential Probiotics Using Nanopore Sequencing and Bioinformatic Analysis

Jirasa Boonsan¹, Kamonnut Singkhamanan¹, Thunchanok Yaikhan¹, Ei Phway Thant¹, Chanida Sakunrang², Monwadee Wonglapsuwan² and Komwit Surachat^{1,3,*}

¹ Department of Biomedical Sciences and Biomedical Engineering, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

² Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

³ Translational Medicine Research Center, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

* Corresponding author: komwit.s@psu.ac.th

Abstract:

This study aimed to screen and evaluate the probiotic properties of bacterial strains isolated from fermented foods and animal feces using nanopore sequencing and bioinformatic analysis. Probiotic microorganisms play a vital role in maintaining gut health and preventing diseases, but traditional methods for identifying and characterizing them are often time-consuming and limited in scope. Advances in sequencing technologies, such as nanopore sequencing, offer a more comprehensive and efficient approach at the genomic level. In this study, thirty bacterial strains were isolated from local foods and animal feces in Songkhla, Thailand. After excluding seven pathogenic strains, the remaining

23 underwent DNA extraction and whole-genome sequencing using the MinION™ platform from Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT). The genomes were assembled and analyzed through bioinformatics to evaluate their probiotic traits and safety profiles. Genome assembly statistics showed significant variability in genome sizes and contig lengths, with N 50 values ranging from 326,094 bp to 3,226,988 bp. None of the 23 strains contained virulence genes linked to major health risks, confirming their safety. Genetic analysis identified key probiotic genes related to acid stress resistance, adhesion, antioxidant activity, bile resistance, and beneficial substance synthesis, underscoring their potential to promote host health. Whole-genome sequencing with ONT, combined with bioinformatic analysis, is an effective method for identifying probiotic strains, predicting their functional properties, and ensuring their safety for consumption.

Keywords: Probiotic, Nanopore sequencing, Bioinformatic Analysis, Bacteria genome, Gene annotation

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by Graduate scholarship, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, whose financial assistance made this research possible. We are also grateful to Prince of Songkla University for providing the infrastructure and resources needed to conduct this study.

Oral Presentation - OR2-05

Unveiling Mobile Genetic Elements: In-Depth Genomic Analysis of Multidrug-Resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* PA12

Thitaporn Dechathai¹, Kamonnut Singkhamanan¹, Thunchanok Yaikhan¹, Sarunyou Chusri², Rattanaruji Pomwised³, Monwadee Wonglapsuwan³, Komwit Surachat^{1,4*}

¹ Department of Biomedical Sciences and Biomedical Engineering, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

² Division of Infectious Diseases, Department of Internal Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

³ Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

⁴ Translational Medicine Research Center, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

* Corresponding author: komwit.s@psu.ac.th

Abstract: Mobile genetic elements (MGEs) are segment of DNA sequences that can self-movement within a genome or facilitate the exchange DNA via horizontal gene transfer (HGT). The elements including integrons, transposon, insertion sequences, genomic islands and plasmids are involved with bacterial evolution and adaptation. This study explored the MGEs present in the *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* PA12 clinical isolate as a multidrug-resistant strain that collected from patient's throat at Songklanagarind Hospital, Southern Thailand. The in-depth data provided through whole genome sequencing. Our findings identified genes associated with transposase (*ins* and *tnp* genes) and a cassette of the *pil* gene involved in Type IV pili (T4P) function. Additionally, a region classified as a Type IV Secretion System (T4SS)-type integrative conjugative element (ICE) was identified. Whereas plasmid was not presence in this strain. Moreover, nine insertion elements were found in the genome sequence which may obtain from numerous bacterial species. as Also, two of each prophage and phages were detected in this genome. This study highlights the critical role of MGEs in the genetic plasticity of MDR-*P. aeruginosa* strain PA12 and offering the importance of these elements in the evolution and dissemination of resistance traits in clinical pathogens.

Keywords: Mobile genetic element, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, whole genome analysis

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by a Graduate Scholarship from the Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University. Additionally, the research was funded by the National Science, Research and Innovation Fund (NSRF) and Prince of Songkla University, Thailand, under grant number MED6701384b. Further support was provided by a Postdoctoral Fellowship from Prince of Songkla University. This project also received funding from the NSRF through the Program Management Unit for Human Resources & Institutional Development, Research and Innovation, under grant number B13F660074.

Oral Presentation - OR2-06

Genomic Analysis and Probiotic Characteristics of *Pediococcus pentosaceus* HN8 with a Focus on GABA Synthesis

**Siriwan Kompramool¹, Kamonnut Singkhamanan¹, Rattanaruji Pomwised²,
Monwadee Wonglapsuwan², Thunchanok Yaikhan¹ and Komwit Surachat^{1,3,*}**

¹ Department of Biomedical Sciences and Biomedical Engineering, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

² Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla, Thailand

³ Translational Medicine Research Center, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

* Correspondence: Corresponding author: komwit.s@psu.ac.th

Abstract: This study explores the probiotic potential of *Pediococcus pentosaceus* HN8, a strain of lactic acid bacteria, was isolated from fermented meat, through comprehensive genome analysis. Using bioinformatics, this research aimed to confirm the strain's safety for probiotic applications and its ability to produce gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), a beneficial neurotransmitter. In prior work, the combination of *P. pentosaceus* HN8 with *Lactobacillus namurensis* NH2 and monosodium glutamate (MSG) resulted in a significant GABA yield of 4051 mg/kg. To ensure its suitability for food applications, this study also examined the strain for virulence factors and bacteriocin production. The whole genome sequence revealed a total size of 2,198,800 base pairs (bp) with a GC content of 38.6%. Several key genes involved in genetic regulation, nutrient transport, metabolic pathways, stress resistance, gut survival, vitamin biosynthesis, and cell adhesion were identified, reinforcing its probiotic properties. Notably, the presence of the glutamate decarboxylase B gene (*gadB*), which is essential to produce GABA, further emphasizes its functional potential production, underscores the strain's value in promoting GABA biosynthesis. These findings highlight the effectiveness of *P. pentosaceus* HN8 as a promising probiotic strain, with a particular focus on its GABA-producing capabilities for commercial food applications.

Keywords: *Pediococcus pentosaceus*, GABA biosynthesis, probiotic potential, glutamate decarboxylase

Acknowledgments: In addition, this research was supported by Graduate Scholarship, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University

Oral Presentation - OR2-07

Phenotypic and Genomic Analysis of *Enterococcus thailandicus* MEDPSU_PRO_001 isolated from Chicken Feces, a potential probiotic with aggregation ability

Thanchanok Muangkaew¹, Kamonnut Singkhamanan¹, Monwadee Wonglapsuwan², Chonticha Romyasamit³, Sirikan Suwannasin¹, Ei Phway Thant¹, Komwit Surachat^{1,4*}

¹ Department of Biomedical Sciences and Biomedical Engineering, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

² Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

³ Department of Medical Technology, School of Allied Health Sciences, Walailak University, Nakhon Si Thammarat, 80161, Thailand

⁴ Translational Medicine Research Center, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

* Corresponding author: komwit.s@psu.ac.th

Abstract: The study meticulously explores the dual nature of *Enterococcus* species, which can function as both opportunistic pathogens and beneficial probiotics depending on the presence of specific virulent factors, by focusing on *Enterococcus thailandicus* MEDPSU_PRO_001, a strain isolated from chicken feces, and aims to comprehensively analyze its genotypic and phenotypic traits through in silico and in vitro methods; utilizing Oxford nanopore long-read sequencing, the study delves into the strain's genomic characteristics to identify critical genetic elements associated with probiotic potential and pathogenicity, such as virulence factor genes, antibiotic resistance genes, and genes linked to adherence and aggregation, with the results revealing a genome size of 2,771,294 bp and the absence of antimicrobial resistance genes at an 80% identity cutoff, although *vanY* (33.91% identity) and *aac(6')-Ii* (72.63% identity) genes were detected, and further supported by phenotypic assays that confirmed the strain's lack of resistance to vancomycin, the identification of adherence-related genes including *ebpA*, *ebpB*, *ebpC*, *srtC*, *ecbA*, *efaA*, and the EPS cluster, and the presence of the bacteriocin-encoding gene *Laps*, while also confirming the strain's lack of hemolytic activity, which all contribute to the conclusion that *E. thailandicus* MEDPSU_PRO_001 possesses significant probiotic potential, particularly in terms of safety and aggregation ability, thereby offering valuable insights into its safe utilization as a probiotic.

Keywords: *Enterococcus thailandicus*, probiotic, pathogen, bioinformatics

Acknowledgments: This research was funded by the National Science, Research and Innovation Fund (NSRF) and Prince of Songkhla University, grant number MED6701384Mc.

Oral Presentation - OR2-08

The Genetic Diversity and Population Study of Mahseer, *Tor tambra* and *Tor tambroides* Distributed in Thailand and Peninsular Malaysia

Krittaporn Lempan¹, Hong-Chiun Lim², Alex Hon-Tsen Yu^{1,3}, and Monwadee Wonglapsuwan^{1,4*}

¹ Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

² Department of Biotechnology, Faculty of Applied Sciences, AIMST University, Sungai Petani 08100, Kedah, Malaysia

³ Department of Life Science, National Taiwan University, Taipei, 10617, Taiwan, Republic of China

⁴ Center for Genomics and Bioinformatics Research, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

*Correspondence e-mail: [monwadee.wo@psu.ac.th]

Abstract: *Tor tambra* is a cyprinid fish in the Mahseer group known as true mahseer. The mahseer have distributed in Vietnam in the east and China in the north, Laos, Cambodia, Thailand, Malaysia, Brunei and Indonesia, including India, Nepal, Bhutan and Bangladesh Sri Lanka, Pakistan and Afghanistan. The *T. tambra* is economically important fish in Thailand because they have pink color body and high price in the market and the *T. tambroides* were sold with cheaper than *T. tambra*. Nowadays the genetic information of these species in Thailand still lacking. This study used *COI* gene and D-loop region for Molecular marker. The fishes were collected from Hulu Langat, Gua Musang, Sungai Tembat, Endau, Sungai Loh of Malaysia and Narathiwat, Yala, Ratchaburi, Phetchaburi, Kanchanaburi Provinces of Thailand. The product size of *COI* gene around 625 bp. and D-loop region around 1,200 bp. The Phylogenetic trees base on *COI* gene and D-loop region were constructed including with haplotype network base on two molecular markers. The results of phylogenetic trees and haplotype network showed the divergent of the fishes from each location were collected. The results all of Thai fishes were *T. tambra* only while Malaysian fishes included both *T. tambra* and *T. tambroides*.

Keywords: *Tor tambra*, *T. tambroides*, *COI* gene and D-loop region.

Acknowledgments: This research was funded by the National Science, Research and Innovation Fund (NSRF) and Prince of Songkla University, Thailand, grant number SCI6701294S

ORAL PRESENTATION

Track 1

Biology,

Environment and Climate Change

Track 2

Biotechnology,

Biochemistry and Functional Food

Track 3

Bioactive

Natural Products and Biomedicine

Track 4

Bio-sensing

Technology and Data Science

Oral Presentation - OR3-01

Exploring the Potential of Chitin and Its Derivative in Inhibiting the Human Hexokinase Isoform 2 Towards Developing Anti-Dengue Drugs

Fazia Adyani Ahmad Fuad^{1*}, Nur Aqilah Husna Azizi¹, and Suriyea Tanbin¹

¹ Department of Chemical Engineering & Sustainability, Kulliyah of Engineering, International Islamic University Malaysia (IIUM), Jalan Gombak, 53100 Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

* Corresponding author: fazia_adyani@iium.edu.my

Abstract: Dengue fever, caused by the dengue virus (DENV) is a significant global health challenge, with no specific antiviral treatment currently available. The search for novel antiviral agents has led to the exploration of unconventional sources, including natural polymers. Chitin, a biopolymer found mostly in the exoskeletons of arthropods and crustaceans, has emerged as a potential therapeutic candidate due to its unique biological properties. Chitin and its derivative, chitosan, were reported to exhibit antiviral activity against a range of viruses by interfering with viral adhesion and replication processes. This work explores the potential of chitin as an antiviral agent against dengue virus, by focusing on its interactions with human hexokinase isoform 2 (HK2) analysed via *in silico* and *in vitro* analyses. However, further research is needed to fully understand its pharmacokinetics, optimal delivery methods, and long-term effects. In the future, if proven effective, chitin-based therapies could significantly impact dengue management and pave the path towards a novel approach to combating this pervasive viral disease.

Keywords: Chitin, Dengue fever, Human Hexokinase Isoform 2

Acknowledgments: This work was funded by UMP-IIUM Sustainable Research Collaboration (IUMP-SRCG22-002-0002).

Oral Presentation - OR3-02

Biological Activities of Ethanolic Extracts From the Inflorescence of Kluai Namwa (*Musa* ABB CV. “Kluai Namwa”)

Piyapat Aiemcharoen^{1,2}, Yaowapa Sukpondma³, and Decha Sermwittayawong^{1,2*}

¹ Division of Health and Applied Sciences, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla, 90110, Thailand

² Center of Excellence for Biochemistry, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hatyai, Songkhla, 90110, Thailand

³ Division of Physical Science and Center of Excellence for Innovation in Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hatyai, Songkhla, 90110, Thailand

* Corresponding author: decha.s@psu.ac.th

Abstract: The banana inflorescence, also known as the banana blossom, is an edible part of the banana plant that belongs to the Musaceae family. It is one of the most economically significant fruit crops globally. The banana inflorescence is widely recognized for its potential as a rich source of antioxidants, due to its high phytochemical content and notable antioxidant activity. Although previous studies have investigated the antioxidant properties of banana inflorescence, other biological activities of the inflorescence remain unexplored. In this study, banana inflorescences from the 'Kluai Namwa' variety were selected for ethanolic extraction. Extracts were prepared from the flowers, bracts, and entire inflorescences, and their phytochemical composition and antioxidant activities were analyzed. The findings revealed that the extracts contained high levels of carbohydrates and low levels of protein. Among the antioxidant assays performed, the flowers demonstrated the strongest activities in the 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) free radical scavenging, ferric ion reducing antioxidant power (FRAP), and 2,2'-azinobis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonic acid) (ABTS) assays. These results suggest that the Kluai Namwa inflorescence is an effective source of antioxidants. Furthermore, the whole inflorescence extracts significantly suppressed lipid accumulation in 3T3-L1 adipocytes in a dose-dependent manner, suggesting potential anti-obesity properties. These findings highlight several biological activities, including antioxidant and anti-obesity effects, and warrant further investigation.

Keywords: Antioxidant activity, Banana inflorescence, Ethanolic extract, Type 2 diabetes

Acknowledgments: This research project is supported by the National Research Council of Thailand (NRCT) : (Contact No N41A650120)

ORAL PRESENTATION

Track 1

Biology,

Environment and Climate Change

Track 2

Biotechnology,

Biochemistry and Functional Food

Track 3

Bioactive

Natural Products and Biomedicine

Track 4

Bio-sensing

Technology and Data Science

Oral Presentation - OR4-01

A Decade of Crop Monitoring Through Remote Sensing: Insights into Climate Change Impacts on crop practice, case studies Vojvodina from 2013-2023

Predrag Lugonja^{1*}, Tijana Nikolić Lugonja¹, Branislav Pejak¹, Branko Brkljač^{1,2}, Sanja Brdar¹ and Vladimir Crnojević¹

¹ BioSense Institute, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, 21000, Serbia

² Faculty of technical science, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, 21000, Serbia

* Corresponding author: [lugonjap@biosense.rs]

Abstract: Climate change has significantly transformed agricultural practices, necessitating adaptations to sustain crop production. Rising temperatures, shifting precipitation patterns, and increased frequency of extreme weather events alter growing conditions and pest dynamics, prompting a reevaluation of traditional farming methods.

The Landsat series has established a lasting impact on remote sensing, offering a fundamental tool for monitoring environmental changes. A key element of the Landsat program's legacy is its commitment to providing open access to data. This principle was later adopted by the ESA with the Sentinel-2 missions. For the small field monitoring, which dominates in Vojvodina, Northern Serbia, Sentinel-2 provides higher spatial resolution, a more spectral bands, and frequent revisit times.

Over ten years of crop monitoring, we utilized data from both Landsat 8 and Sentinel-2 satellites. To assess the impact of climate change on agricultural practices, we generated two distinct datasets. The first dataset consists of annual crop classification maps, which categorize and map the types of crops grown in each area over the years. The second dataset is a time series of NDVI values for each year, providing a continuous measure of vegetation health.

By analyzing these datasets together, we could track crop distribution changes and identify crop rotation trends. This approach allowed us to correlate changes in agricultural practices with climatic variations, offering a comprehensive understanding of how climate change influences crop productivity and land use year by year.

Our study reveals several shifts in agricultural practices, including introducing some new crops in Vojvodina. The overall pace of adaptation could be faster. The NDVI time series data indicates a significant increase in droughts.

The research indicates that the adaptation process for farmers is progressing at a slow rate, so it is crucial to offer comprehensive support to farmers. This support should begin with conducting detailed research to determine which crop or crop varieties are best suited for the local conditions. Following

the research phase, it is important to focus on education and training for farmers. Providing them with the necessary knowledge and skills will enable them to implement the recommended practices and adapt to changing conditions more effectively.

Keywords: Crop Monitoring, Remote Sensing, Climate Change

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by the Horizon 2020 Antares project under the European Union's research and innovation program (grant agreement No. 739570). We extend our gratitude to our colleagues from the Remote Sensing Group from Center for Information Technologies for their invaluable assistance with fieldwork over the past 10 years.

Oral Presentation - OR4-02

Design Challenges in the Development of Porta-ble Peritoneal Dialysis Prototype Module in Malaysia

Mohd Zulhakimi Ab Razak^{1,*}, Abdul Hafiz Mat Sulaiman¹, and Nor Syahira Mohd Tombel¹

¹ *Institute of Microengineering and Nanoelectronics (IMEN), Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, 43600 Bangi, Selangor, Malaysia*

* Corresponding author: zul.hakimi@ukm.edu.my

Abstract: Chronic kidney disease is a significant public health concern with an ever-increasing prevalence of chronic kidney disease (CKD) and end-stage renal disease (ESRD) in Malaysia, and over 2 million people are currently suffering from ESRD Worldwide. The prevalence of CKD has increased from 9.1% in the 2011 National Health and Morbidity survey to 15.5% in 2018. The Malaysian Dialysis and Transplant Registry reported that 7,628 new patients received dialysis in 2014 and the number had increased to 8,552 in 2018. In 2022, there were 9,295 new patients on dialysis were recorded. Peritoneal dialysis (PD) is one of dialysis treatments for a patient who is at 'Stage Five' of CKD, which is also known as 'end-stage' renal failure. At this stage, the kidney is no longer functioning, and the blood circulation needs to be filtered in order to maintain good health. This kind of dialysis requires an amount of dialysate to exchange into and out of the patient's body. Similar to the hemodialysis procedure, a PD patient needs to undergo a 4-hour treatment, 3 times a week, with very limited movement or activities. Therefore, IMEN in Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia has taken an initiative since 2018 to develop a prototype of portable PD module that enables a patient to do other light activities while undergoing PD treatment. While the laboratory prototype of the portable PD module was successfully developed, there are several design challenges that need to be tackled in order to make the prototype ready for the market. The developed module, although, has demonstrated the function that mimics conventional PD procedure, there is still room for technical improvements in terms of medicine and engineering perspectives. Therefore, we describe the engineering design of a portable PD module that had been developed and discuss the design challenges, especially when the design process involves and across multi-disciplinary areas including science, engineering, electronics, and medicine. Here, we propose a design octagon as a guideline. In summary, the adaptation process of engineering in biomedical field requires careful consideration and meticulous technical discussion to ensure the transition process is smooth, fast, and successful.

Keywords: Peritoneal Dialysis, Portable Prototype, Engineering, Challenge, CKD, ESRD

Acknowledgments: This research work was supported by the Ministry of Higher Education (MOHE) Malaysia and University Kebangsaan Malaysia (UKM) under Fundamental Research Grant Scheme (Grant code: FRGS/1/2020/STG07/UKM/02/3), and Ministry of Science Technology and Innovation (MOSTI) with the grant code PR1217Q1145.

Oral Presentation - OR4-03

Smartphone-enabled electrochemical point-of-care testing for SARS-CoV-2 detection

Atchara Lomae^{1,2}, Charles S. Henry^{3,4}, Ekawat Pasomsub⁵, Angsana Phuphuakrat⁶, Tirayut Vilaivan⁷, Orawon Chailapakul², Nipapan Ruecha^{2,3}, and Nattaya Ngamrojanavanich^{2,8*}**

¹Center of Excellence of Trace Analysis and Biosensor, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hatyai, Songkhla 90112, Thailand

²Electrochemistry and Optical Spectroscopy Center of Excellence (EOSCE), Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, 10330, Thailand

³Metallurgy and Materials Science Research Institute, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, 10330, Thailand

⁴Department of Chemistry, Colorado State University, Fort Collins, CO, 80523, USA

⁵Department of Pathology, Faculty of Medicine Ramathibodi Hospital, Mahidol University, Bangkok, 10400, Thailand

⁶Department of Medicine, Faculty of Medicine Ramathibodi Hospital, Mahidol University, Bangkok, 10400, Thailand

⁷Organic Synthesis Research Unit, Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, 10330, Thailand

⁸Institute of Biotechnology and Genetic Engineering, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, 10330, Thailand

* Corresponding author: nipapan.r@chula.ac.th (N. Ruecha), nattaya.n@chula.ac.th (N. Ngamrojanavanich)

Abstract: Following the COVID-19 pandemic, the need for rapid, reliable, and affordable point-of-care diagnostic devices remains urgent. Although COVID-19 is no longer considered an emergency, it continues to pose a significant threat to human health. In response to this need, we present a smartphone-assisted Sensit Smart potentiostat (PalmSens) integrated with a paper-based electrochemical sensor for detecting severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). The working electrode was screen-printed onto the paper-based analytical device (μ PAD). The hydroxy-rich natural cellulose paper beneath the working electrode is directly modified with a pyrrolidiny peptide nucleic acid (acpcPNA) as the biological recognition element to capture the target SARS-CoV-2 DNA. Additionally, the working electrode was separately screen-printed from the counter and reference electrode to prevent contamination during sample introduction. The detection mechanism relies on the impedance of the redox conversion of a redox reporter on the electrode surface, resulting in a decrease in the electrochemical response correlation to SARS-CoV-2 concentration. Our device demonstrates excellent efficiency in diagnosing COVID-19 with the applicability to detect SARS-CoV-2 in the range from 0.1 to 200 nM and a detection limit of 1.0 pM. Due to the high specificity of the acpcPNA-based electrochemical paper-based analytical device toward SARS-CoV-2 (DNA), this device was applied to detect amplification-free SARS-CoV-2 in 10 nasopharyngeal swab samples (7 SARS-CoV-2 positive and 3 SARS-CoV-2 negative), providing a 100% agreement result with RT-PCR.

Keywords: COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, Paper-based device, acpcPNA probe

References:

Lomae A, Preechakasedkit P, Hanpanich O, Ozer T, Henry CS, Maruyama A, Pasomsub E, Phuphuakrat A, Rengpipat S, Vilaivan T, Chailapakul O, Ruecha N, Ngamrojanavanich N. Label free electrochemical DNA biosensor for COVID-19 diagnosis. *Talanta*. 2023;253:123992.

Lomae A, Teekayupak K, Preechakasedkit P, Pasomsub E, Ozer T, Henry CS, Citterio D, Vilaivan T, Chailapakul O, Ruecha N. Peptide nucleic acid probe-assisted paper-based electrochemical biosensor for multiplexed detection of respiratory viruses. *Talanta*. 2024;279:12661

Oral Presentation - OR4-04

Smartphone-enabled flow injection amperometric glucose monitoring based on a screen-printed carbon electrode modified with PEDOT@PB and a GOx@PPtNPs@MWCNTs nanocomposite

Suntisak Khumngern^{1,2}, Natha Nontipichet¹, Panote Thavarungkul^{1,2,3}, Proespichaya Kanatharana^{1,2,3}, and Apon Numnuam^{1,2,3,*}

¹ Center of Excellence for Trace Analysis and Biosensor, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla, 90110, Thailand

² Division of Physical Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla, 90110, Thailand

³ Center of Excellence for Innovation in Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla, 90110, Thailand

* Corresponding author: apon.n@psu.ac.th

Abstract: A novel flow injection amperometric glucose biosensor was developed by modifying a poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) and Prussian blue (PEDOT@PB) nanocomposite and glucose oxidase on porous platinum nanoparticles decorated on multi-walled carbon nanotubes (GOx@PPtNPs@MWCNTs) nanocomposite on a screen-printed carbon electrode. The PEDOT@PB nanocomposite was used as a high-conductive and electrocatalytic activity redox mediator for the detection of H₂O₂, the byproduct of the GOx-catalyzed oxidation of glucose. This allowed to detect H₂O₂ at the applied operational potential of -0.10 V, reducing interference from electroactive compounds. The PPtNPs@MWCNTs nanocomposite exhibited excellent electrochemical characteristics such as high surface area, high conductivity, and high electron transfer rates. Furthermore, this nanocomposite demonstrated high GOx immobilization efficiency, which was attributed to the high surface area and high porosity of PPtNPs. The fabricated electrode accurately and sensitively measured H₂O₂ and was then applied as a glucose biosensor. The modified electrode was used in an FIA system that measured glucose based on amperometric detection, enabling continuous detection, low sample consumption, good repeatability, and ease of operation. Under optimal conditions, the developed biosensor produced a linear range from 2.50 μM to 1.250 mM, a limit of detection of 2.50 μM, operational stability over 500 sample injections, and good selectivity. The proposed biosensing system determined glucose in human plasma samples, achieving recoveries and results that agreed with the hexokinase-spectrophotometric method (P > 0.05). Combining the proposed biosensor with the custom-built sample feed, a portable potentiostat and a smartphone, enabled on-site glucose monitoring.

Keywords: Diabetes, Glucose, Biosensor, Flow injection system, PPtNPs@MWCNTs nanocomposite

Acknowledgments: This project was supported by the National Science, Research and Innovation Fund (NSRF) and Prince of Songkla University (Grant No. SCI6601074S). Partial support is

acknowledged from the National Research Council of Thailand (NRCT, N42A650252), the Center of Excellence for Innovation in Chemistry (PERCH-CIC), Ministry of Higher Education, Science, Research and Innovation and Center of Excellence for Trace Analysis and Biosensor (TAB-CoE), Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Thailand. The authors acknowledge the Talent Management Project of Prince of Songkla University.

Oral Presentation - OR4-05

Enzymatic uric acid biosensor based on AuNPs–GO–CS porous cryogel coated on PB–PEDOT:PSS modified screen-printed carbon electrode

Thanawath Tuntiwongmetee^{1,2,3}, Suntisak Khumngern^{1,2}, Natha Nontipichet¹,
Supapich Romportong^{1,2,3}, Panote Thavarungkul^{1,2,3}, Proespichaya Kanatharana^{1,2,3}, and
Apon Numnuam^{1,2,3,*}

¹ Center of Excellence for Trace Analysis and Biosensor, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

² Division of Physical Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

³ Center of Excellence for Innovation in Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

* Corresponding author: apon.n@psu.ac.th

Abstract:

An enzymatic amperometric uric acid (UA) biosensor was successfully developed based on a screen-printed carbon electrode (SPCE) modified with Prussian blue-poly(3,4-ethylene dioxythiophene) polystyrene sulfonate composite (PB-PEDOT:PSS). The modified electrode was coated with gold nanoparticles-graphene oxide-chitosan cryogel (AuNPs–GO–CS cry). The enzyme uricase (UOx) was directly immobilized onto AuNPs via chemisorption. UA was determined using amperometric detection with a flow injection analysis (FIA) based on PB's reduction current which was correlated with the H₂O₂ produced during the enzymatic reaction. Under optimal conditions, the fabricated UA biosensor produced a linear range from 5.0 to 300 μmol L⁻¹ with a limit of detection at 1.88 μmol L⁻¹. The proposed sensor was stable for up to 221 detection times and rapid analysis time (2 min), with excellent reproducibility (RSDs <2.90 %, n =6), anti-interferences, and acceptable recoveries from 94.0 ±3.9 to 101.1 ±2.6 %. The results of UA determination in 20 human blood plasma samples agreed with the enzymatic colorimetric method from Songklanagarind Hospital (P >0.05).

Keywords: [Uric acid biosensor, Uricase enzyme, Prussian blue–poly(3,4-ethylene dioxythiophene) polystyrene sulfonate composite, Gold nanoparticles–graphene oxide–chitosan composite cryogel]

Acknowledgments: This project was supported by the National Research Council of Thailand (NRCT, N42A650252). Financial support for Thanawath Tuntiwongmetee was kindly provided by the Faculty of Science Research Fund, Prince of Songkla University (Contract no. 1-2565-02- 001), the Center of Excellence for Innovation in Chemistry (PERCH- CIC), and the Center of Excellence for Trace Analysis and Biosensor (TAB-CoE). We would like to thank Mr. Thomas Duncan Coyne for his English language review.

POSTER PRESENTATION

POSTER PRESENTATION

Track 1

Biology,

Environment and Climate Change

Track 2

Biotechnology,

Biochemistry and Functional Food

Track 3

Bioactive

Natural Products and Biomedicine

Track 4

Bio-sensing

Technology and Data Science

Poster Presentation - P1-01

Year-round Occurrence of Crustacean Holoplanktons in Mae Klong River Mouth as Indicator of Natural Food in Gulf of Thailand

Bongkot Wichachucherd^{1*}, Sirinya Sirimahawan¹, Panisa Duanghwang², and Eknarin Rodcharoen²

¹ Department of Science and Bioinnovation, Faculty of Liberal Arts and Science, Kasetsart University, Kamphaeng Saen, Nakhon Pathom 73140. Thailand.

² Aquatic Science and Innovative Management Division, Faculty of Natural Resources; and Discipline of Excellence for Sustainable Aquaculture, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla 90110. Thailand.

* Corresponding author: bongkot.w@ku.th

Abstract:

Currently, climate change is causing critical global environmental variation. Rising of temperature is caused by the climate change perceived in many areas. Temperature is the dominant factor affecting organisms, including crustacean holoplanktons that are the primary group of food providers in ecosystem for aquatic animal nursery grounds. Also, river mouth is the importance area serving physiochemical fluctuation. Sampling was carried out in three seasons year-round at Don Hoi Lod (DH) and Mae Klong River (MK) in Samut Songkhram province, Thailand. The 100 ml of water samples were collected at 30 cm depth and then filtered through plankton net. Samples were preserved in 10% formaldehyde seawater then they were identified in the laboratory. The density estimation was done by number of individuals per water volume. Water and air temperature, pH and salinity were primary physical record from the field stations. The relationship between crustacean holoplankton and environmental factors were analyzed by canonical correspondence analysis. The results showed that salinity and temperature showed the similar pattern between DH and MK. Otherwise, the physical factors changed in significantly different seasons. A total of two main taxa of Copepods and Cladocerans were found in two stations. There were a variety of copepod group into Order Calanoida, Cyclopoida, Harpacticoida and nauplius copepod. The data also showed that only the copepod group was identified year-round in both areas, albeit, at different densities. DH had a higher species richness than MK. Seasonal change had much influence on the similarity of holoplanktons on two stations. In addition, the overall population of crustacean holoplanktons significantly decreased with increased temperature. Seasonal change may have been a factor affecting the biodiversity of crustacean holoplanktons and other planktons. The results of this study should inform and highlight biodiversity of planktons at river mouth.

Keywords: Seasonal change, Crustacean, Holoplankton, Mangrove, Zooplankton

Acknowledgments: This work was funded by Biological Science undegraded research funding from Department of Liberal Arts and Science and Sciences Research Promotion and Technology Transfer Center (*contract number 202/2564*), Faculty of Liberal Arts and Science Kasetsart University (Kamphaeng Saen campus)

Poster Presentation - P1-02

Heavy metals accumulation (As, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, Cu and Cd) in vegetables grown on polluted soil and consumers health assessment

Slobodanka Pajević^{1*}, Nataša Nikolić¹, Danijela Arsenov¹, Milan Borišev¹, and Milica Popić²

¹ University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Novi Sad, Serbia

² University of Priština in Kosovska Mitrovica, Faculty of Sciences and Mathematics, Kosovska Mitrovica

* Corresponding author: slobodanka.pajevic@dbe.uns.ac.rs

Abstract:

The loading of agricultural soil with various potentially toxic trace elements has become a serious concern across the world, due to their possible translocation in cultivated plants. Accumulation of these elements in plant organs reduces their quality and safety for human consumption, due to a plant's pollution and modification of metabolic pathways and bioactive compounds production. The cultivation of vegetables and medicinal plants should be strictly regulated and controlled in accordance with the standards of healthy food production.

The aim of the present study was evaluation of quality and safety of celery (*Apium graveolens*) and parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*) cultivated in Cd polluted soil. We examined the presence of potentially toxic trace elements (PTEs): As, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, Cu and Cd in soil and studied species, as well as their physiological responses to different Cd exposures (control–without Cd addition, 3 and 6 µg/g Cd of dry soil). The plants were grown in greenhouse using sandy fluvisol for 5 weeks in a completely randomized block design, in 6 treatments: C0–celery control, C3–celery with 3 µg/g Cd, C6–celery with 6 µg/g Cd, P0–parsley control, P3–parsley with 3 µg/g Cd, P6–parsley with 6 µg/g Cd, with 3 replicates per treatment. Optimal soil moisture of 60–70% was kept. Temperature ranged between 22 and 30°C, while light condition was 16/8 h day/night. The concentration of PTEs was measured by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry. The tolerance index, bioaccumulation factor, human health risk, plant tolerance and physiological parameters were determined. Following elevation of Cd in plants, both species showed increasing trend of As, Pb and Cu in plants, which overcome safe limits, with exception for Cu. Celery showed strong phytoextraction ability with high potential to tolerate Cd due to the efficient antioxidative machinery. Investigated hazard quotients (HQ), hazard index (HI) and cancerogenic risk (CR), indicated that chronic consumption of contaminated herbs can consequently endanger human health. Toxicological analyzes must be carried out continuously, and the (bio) chemical characteristics of the plants consumed should represent the most important parameters that determine the use / further purpose.

Keywords: soil Cd-contamination, celery, parsley, phytoextraction potential, human health risk

Poster Presentation - P1-03

Combining the use of Mosses and Snails as Bio-indicators of Heavy Metal Air Pollution

Tania Russo¹, Alessia Di Fraia¹, Viviana Maresca^{2,*}, Alessia Postiglione¹, Carmen Arena¹, and Adriana Basile Gianluca Polese¹

1 Department of Biology, University of Naples Federico II, via Vicinale Cupa Cintia 26, 80126, Naples, Italy

2 Department of Life Sciences, Health and Health Professions, University of Rome "link Campus", Rome, Italy

* Corresponding author: v.maresca@unilink.it

Abstract: Air pollution is a significant threat to both human health and the environment, with heavy metal contamination being one of the most critical concerns. Heavy metals are particularly dangerous due to their prolonged persistence in the atmosphere, high toxicity, and their tendency to accumulate in living organisms, including humans, through the process of bioaccumulation. These metals highly impact ecosystems, contaminating air, water, and soil. Continuous monitoring of air pollution, especially heavy metal levels, is crucial for safeguarding human, animal, and environmental health. Traditional detection methods are often limited by high costs, complex data processing, and the inability to capture the synergistic effects of pollutants. Fortunately, innovative and cost-effective biomonitoring techniques using living organisms are gaining attention. Among these, mosses and snails are emerging as key bioindicators. Their success is attributed not only to their structural simplicity but also to their ability to be relocated, allowing biomonitoring across diverse sites.

This study evaluated heavy metal pollution in two areas of southern Italy combining the use of mosses (*Rhytidiadelphus squarrosus*) and snails (*Helix aspersa*). The selected study areas were Montemiletto, a relatively unpolluted rural region in the Irpinia hills, and Giugliano in Campania, an area heavily contaminated by human activities such as industrial activities and illegal waste incineration.

After acclimatization, the organisms were exposed to the sites for 30 days. Post-exposure, heavy metal concentrations, oxidative stress biomarkers, and histopathological and ultra-structural analyses were assessed. Organisms exposed to the Giugliano area accumulated significantly higher concentrations of heavy metals including lead, cadmium, iron, mercury, and magnesium. Furthermore, antioxidant defenses, such as catalase and glutathione-S-transferases, were activated in both organisms. The mosses showed less ultrastructural damage. However, in snails exposed to the Giugliano area, an increase in histopathological alterations was observed despite these protective mechanisms.

These findings demonstrate that mosses and snails, especially when used in combination, are highly effective bioindicators and bioaccumulators, making them valuable tools for monitoring heavy metal pollution in the air.

Keywords: Heavy Metal pollution, Biomonitoring, Oxidative stress Biomarkers, Histopathology

Acknowledgments: This research was funded by MISE title: LIFECYCLE INDUSTRIAL MANAGER BIOSENSOR BASED.

Poster Presentation - P1-04

Protective effect of *Ocimum basilicum* L. essential oil on *Lactuca sativa* L. treated with cadmium

Simone Landi^{1†}, Flavio Polito^{2†}, Sergio Esposito¹, Sergio Sorbo³, Piergiorgio Cianciullo¹, Vincenzo De Feo², Adriana Basile^{1*}, Viviana Maresca¹

¹ Dipartimento di Biologia, University of Naples Federico II, Complesso Univ. Monte Sant'Angelo, Via Cinthia 4, 80126 Napoli, Italy

² Department of Pharmacy, University of Salerno, Via Giovanni Paolo II, 132, Fisciano, 84084, Italy

³ Ce.S.M.A, Section of Microscopy, University of Naples Federico II, Complesso Univ. Monte Sant'Angelo, Via Cinthia 4, 80126 Napoli, Italy

[†] These authors contributed equally to this work.

* Corresponding author: adbasile@unina.it

Abstract:

In recent years, essential oils (EOs) arose as a sustainable and effective alternative to conventional chemical treatments in response to HMs in plants. These natural molecules can enhance plant resilience under stress. In the present work, the ability of EOs of the aerial parts of *Ocimum basilicum* L. cv "Prospera" to improve the response of plants to HMs, was investigated in lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.) subjected to Cd. The chemical profile of the essential oil (EO) was investigated by GC-MS, reporting a composition by oxygenated monoterpenes, with *endo*-fenchol (21.5%) and eugenol (20.4%) as the main constituents. The EO-induced tolerance to different Cd concentrations (360 μ M and 720 μ M) was studied analyzing ultrastructural damage, antioxidant response and changes in expression of genes involved in the abiotic stress response. Our results indicated that exogenous application of basil EO helps to preserve the correct ultrastructure of plastids and ameliorates damages induced by Cd. Furthermore, reduces the production of ROS and beneficial regulation of the activities and of the molecular expression of antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT) and glutathione-S-transferase (GST) were reported. In conclusion, these results clearly indicate the protective capacity of basil EO on the cytological organization and in modulating the redox state through the antioxidant pathway by reducing Cd-induced oxidative stress.

Keywords: Essential oil, Cadmium, Antioxidant activity, TEM, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Lactuca sativa*

Poster Presentation - P1-05

Effect of Chronic High-Sugar Consumption on Behavior Adaptation in Mice

Rapeepan Kongnual^{1,2*} , and [Dania Cheaha]^{1,2}.

¹ *Division of Biological Science (Biology Program), Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hatyai, Songkhla, 90110, Thailand*

² *Biosignal Research Center for Health, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hatyai, Songkhla, 90110, Thailand*

* Corresponding author: rapeepan689@gmail.com

Abstract:

Excess of sugar consumption has become increasingly prevalent, affecting both adults and children. Although it is widely recognized that high sugar intake contributes to various health complications such as obesity, type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular disease, fatty liver disease, and chronic inflammation. However, its effects on the brain function, particularly in cognitive processes, are less understood. Therefore, this study investigates the effects of chronic sugar consumption on behavioral adaptation and motivational food reward in mice, using a T-maze food preference test. We compared the behavior of mice subjected to an 8-week high-sugar diet with those on a control diet. The T-maze, a widely used tool in behavioral neuroscience, allows for the assessment of cognitive functions such as learning and decision-making. In this study, mice were allowed to freely explore the T-maze for 15 minutes, one arm containing the high-sugar diet and the other containing the control diet. Our results demonstrated that the mice exposed to high-sugar diet group exhibited significant weight gain and increased caloric consumption compared to the control group. Furthermore, in the T-maze test, mice fed a high-sugar diet had a significant preference for spending time in the arm associated with the high-sugar diet, revealing that chronic sugar consumption can alter the motivational response to food reward. These findings suggest that chronic high-sugar consumption not only affects metabolic health, but also has profound implications for behavior and cognitive function.

Keywords: high-sugar diet, behavior, T-maze

Acknowledgments: This work was funded by The Development and Promotion of Science and Technology Talents Project. , Faculty of Science , Prince of Songkla University

Poster Presentation - P1-06

Influence of Seasonal Variations on the Anatomical and Physiological Characteristics of *Launaea sarmentosa* (Willd.) Kuntze (Asteraceae) of the Andaman Coast, Thailand

Yurachat Meksuwan^{1*}, Pornsawan Sutthinon², and Phuripong Meksuwan³

¹ Faculty of Technology and Environment, Prince of Songkla University, Phuket Campus, Phuket, 83120 Thailand.

² Department of Botany, Faculty of Science, Kasetsart University, Bangkok, 10900, Thailand.

³ Science and Mathematics Program (Biology), Faculty of Science and Technology, Phuket Rajabhat University, Phuket, 83000 Thailand

* Corresponding author: yurachat.y@phuket.psu.ac.th

Abstract: The populations of *Launaea sarmentosa* (Willd.) Kuntze along the Andaman coast have critically declined, largely due to habitat degradation. In this study, we aim to examine the anatomical and physiological adaptations of the species to understand its seasonal dynamics, predict ecosystem responses, and promote conservation strategies. Four study sites where *Launaea sarmentosa* (Willd.) Kuntze naturally grows were Bor Dan Beach (S1) and Natai Beach (S2) in Phang Nga Province, along with Sai Kaew Beach (S3) and Mai Khao Beach (S4) in Phuket Province, Southern Thailand. During the rainy and dry seasons, we examined shoot density (shoots/m²), fresh weight, and biomass of above- and below-ground plant parts (g/m²), as well as chlorophyll and carotenoid content (µg/g FW). Additionally, we investigated the anatomical features of leaves, stems, and roots, including the number of epidermal cell layers, epidermal thickness, size of epidermal cells, height of palisade and spongy cells, size of laminar air spaces, thickness and length of the midrib, midrib xylem thickness, xylem area, stomatal length, and stomatal density on both the adaxial and abaxial surfaces. Here we presented the key findings of this study, which include: (1) Shoot density revealed significant differences across both the seasons and the study sites; (2) The fresh weight of the above-ground part was higher than that of the below-ground part, whereas the biomass data showed the opposite trend, suggesting that the below-ground part plays a crucial role in the plant's survival; (3) During the dry season, the exposure of the habitat (light intensity) had a strong positive influence on both chlorophyll and carotenoid content, whereas in the rainy season, this influence was less evident. (4) Certain anatomical features of the leaves responded to seasonal variations, while the root anatomy demonstrated adaptations to the environmental conditions of the study sites.

Keywords: Coastal plant, Epidermal cells, Above ground biomass, Below ground biomass

Acknowledgments: This work was funded by National Science, Research and Innovation Fund (NSRF) (TAE6701285S) and Prince of Songkla University, Phuket Campus (TAE6703054S-0).

POSTER PRESENTATION

Track 1

Biology,

Environment and Climate Change

Track 2

Biotechnology,

Biochemistry and Functional Food

Track 3

Bioactive

Natural Products and Biomedicine

Track 4

Bio-sensing

Technology and Data Science

Poster Presentation - P2-01

Acetic acid pretreatment effects on biogas production from sewage sludge

Anita Leovac Maćerak*, Dragana Žmukić, Nataša Duduković, Nataša Slijepčević, Aleksandra Kulić Mandić, Gordana Vlahović, Đurđa Kerkez

Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, 21000, Serbia

* Corresponding author: anita.leovac@dh.uns.ac.rs

Abstract: Recycling sewage sludge, is crucial for reaching carbon neutrality in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). Anaerobic digestion (AD) is a cost-effective and easy process for reducing sludge pollution and converting organic fractions into value-added products. Sludge pretreatment prior to anaerobic fermentation is crucial for accelerating sludge hydrolysis and removing competing inhibitors. This study aimed to employ acetic acid as a non-aggressive acid, to directly treat sewage sludge in batch AD experiments. The objective was to evaluate the production of biogas from anaerobic digestion (AD) using raw sludge as substrate and supernatant after AD as inoculum, both taken from WWTP of nominal capacity of 150 000 equivalent per capita (EC). The total solids (TS) content of the raw sludge was 4.35%, and the volatile solids (VS) accounted for 74% (w/w) of TS. The evaluation of the methane production potential was performed in a bench-scale experiment using the biochemical methane potential (BMP) test in mesophilic conditions. The inoculum-to-substrate ratio used was 2:1. The dosages of acetic acid were in the range of 1 mM – 5 mM. The BMP tests lasted 10 days. Results showed that biogas production of AD batches with acetic acid pretreatment at 4 mM and 5 mM on AD were effectively enhanced, with the highest production being 2.7 and 3.6 times of that observed in control AD without acetic acid treatment. However, the AD batches with acetic acid treatment at low dosages of 1-3 mM had lower methane production (~1.5 times). The average VS removal effectiveness of 33% indicates a reduction of VS in the analyzed treatment. Total and soluble carbohydrates were consumed in AD process with an average percentage respectively of 74%-84%, while breakdown of total proteins concentration reach about of 40% at the highest dosage. Results show that acetic acid significantly promotes sludge disruption and increases dissolved material quantities and enhances the degradation and conversion of macromolecular organic matter (e.g., proteins and polysaccharides). Detailed mechanism will be elucidated in the future. The obtained results have to be considered as preliminary data to point out main characteristics and the anaerobic biodegradability of pre-treated sewage sludge.

Keywords: Anaerobic digestion, Sewage Sludge, Biogas, BMP tests

References:

Tang, Y., Sun, J., Dong, B., Dai, X (2023) Citric acid treatment directly on anaerobic digester sludge alleviates the inhibitory effect of in-situ generated humic acids by their deconstruction and redistribution. *Water Research*, 233, 119680.

Filer, J., Ding, H., Chang, S. (2019) Biochemical Methane Potential (BMP) Assay Method for Anaerobic Digestion Research. *Water* 2019, 11, 921; doi:10.3390/w11050921.

Acknowledgments: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, Horizon Europe - Work Programme 2021–2022 Widening participation and strengthening the European Research Area, HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-02, under grant agreement No [101060110], SmartWaterTwin

Poster Presentation - P2-02

Phenotypic and Genotypic Study Through Virulence and Antibiotic Resistance of *Enterococcus avium* MC09 from Mud Crab

Sirikan Suwannasin¹, Kamonnut Singkhamanan¹, Rattanaruji Pomwised², Thunchanok Yaikhan¹, Nattarika Chaichana^{1,2}, Monwadee Wonglapsuwan² and Komwit Surachat^{1,3,*}

¹ Department of Biomedical Sciences and Biomedical Engineering, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

² Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla, Thailand

³ Translational Medicine Research Center, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

* Corresponding author: komwit.s@psu.ac.th

Abstract: *Enterococcus avium*, a species isolated from various environmental sources, has raised concerns about its role as a potential reservoir for antibiotic resistance. In this study, *E. avium* strain MC09, isolated from a mud crab in a Thai market, was analyzed for its antibiotic resistance and pathogenic potential. The presence of *E. avium* in seafood is significant, as it suggests that seafood could serve as a reservoir for antibiotic-resistant bacteria, posing public health risks along the food chain. Antibiotic susceptibility testing, using the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method, revealed that the strain is resistant to clindamycin, erythromycin, streptomycin, and tetracycline, and exhibits alpha (α) hemolysis on blood agar. The draft genome of MC09 was sequenced using long-read technology on the Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) platform, resulting in 13 contigs, including three L₅₀ contigs. The genome spans 4,583,842 bp, with an average G+C content of 39.1%, and contains 6514 coding sequences (CDS), 17 rRNA genes, 64 tRNA genes, and 1 tmRNA gene. PathogenFinder analysis indicated an 80.2% probability that MC09 could be a potential human pathogen. Genomic sequencing identified resistance genes for macrolides (*ermB*) and tetracyclines (*tetL* and *tetM*). Additionally, several virulence-associated genes were detected, indicating crucial roles in adhesion, immune evasion, biofilm formation, and host colonization, contributing to the pathogenic potential of the strain. Furthermore, several insertion sequences (ISs) were identified, including *IS1216*, *IS1216E*, *IS1216V*, *IS6770*, *ISEfa7*, *ISEfa8*, and *ISS1W*, which are commonly associated with pathogenicity and adaptability in *Enterococcus* strains. This study provides a detailed analysis of both the phenotypic and genotypic features of *E. avium* MC09, highlighting its antimicrobial resistance and pathogenic potential, and emphasizes the importance of monitoring antibiotic resistance in bacteria associated with seafood.

Keywords: *Enterococcus avium*, Antibiotic Resistance, Virulence factors, Bioinformatic Analysis

Acknowledgments: This research was funded by the National Science, Research and Innovation Fund (NSRF) and Prince of Songkla University, Thailand, grant number MED6701384c. This study also was funded by the NSRF through the Program Management Unit for Human Resources & Institutional Development, Research, and Innovation, under grant number B13F660076

Poster Presentation - P2-03

The Whole Genome Analysis of *Mangrovibacter phragmitis* PSU-3885-11 Isolated from a Patient in Thailand

Nattarika Chaichana^{1,4}, Thunchanok Yaikhan¹, Mingkwan Yingkajorn², Nonthawat Thepsimanon², Sirikan Suwannasin¹, Kamonnut Singkhamanan¹, Sarunyou Chusri³, Rattanaruji Pomwised⁴, Monwadee Wonglapsuwan⁴ and Komwit Surachat^{1,5,*}

¹ Department of Biomedical Sciences and Biomedical Engineering, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

² Department of Pathology, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

³ Division of Infectious Diseases, Department of Internal Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

⁴ Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

⁵ Translational Medicine Research Center, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

* Correspondence: komwit.s@psu.ac.th

Abstract: *Mangrovibacter phragmitis* is a Gram-negative bacterium traditionally associated with plant roots, contributing to nitrogen fixation and enhancing plant growth in nutrient-poor environments such as mangrove ecosystems. Although primarily found in environmental niches, this *M. phragmitis* was unexpectedly isolated from a human patient in Thailand. In this study, we report the whole genome sequence (WGS) of *M. phragmitis* strain PSU-3885-11, isolated from the sputum of a 29-year-old female patient with spinal tuberculosis. The isolate was initially misidentified as part of the *Enterobacter cloacae* complex through MALDI-TOF analysis; however, WGS subsequently confirmed its correct identity as *M. phragmitis*. Its complete genome spans 5,035,050 bp with a GC content of 50%, containing 4,651 coding sequences, 72 tRNA genes, and 1 tmRNA. Comparative genomic analysis showed a 99.32% average nucleotide identity (ANI) with the reference strain *M. phragmitis* MP23. Moreover, several antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) and mobile genetic elements (MGEs) were identified in the *M. phragmitis* genome which may contribute to its ability to survive in diverse environments, including human hosts. Notably, PSU-3885-11 exhibited resistance to beta-lactam antibiotics such as ampicillin and cefotaxime, while remaining sensitive to a wide range of other antibiotics. Virulence factor analysis identified key genes involved in host adaptation, stress response, and bacterial interactions, including *ompA*, *hcp/issD*, and *rpoS*, which are highly conserved across various *Mangrovibacter* strains. These genes may play critical roles in bacterial ability to persist within a human host which highlights its potential as an opportunistic pathogen. In addition, the detection of ribosomally synthesized and post-translationally modified peptides (RiPPs) and bacteriocins suggests that *M. phragmitis* PSU-3885-11 may possess antimicrobial properties, potentially providing a competitive advantage in both environmental and clinical settings. Therefore, this study provides valuable insights into the genomic features,

antibiotic resistance, and potential pathogenicity of *M. phragmitis* PSU-3885-11. The findings emphasize the importance of continued surveillance and genomic analysis of environmental bacteria that may emerge as opportunistic pathogens in human infections.

Keywords: Whole Genome Sequencing, *Mangrovibacter phragmitis*, Bioinformatics, Antibiotic Resistance, Mobile Genetic Elements

Acknowledgments: This work was funded by the NSRF through the Program Management Unit for Human Resources & Institutional Development, Research, and Innovation, under grant numbers B13F660074 and B13F670076. Additionally, this research was provided by the Postdoctoral Fellowship from Prince of Songkla University, Thailand.

Poster Presentation - P2-04

Germ cell grafting in banana shrimp for sustainable aquaculture

Jaruwan Boonchuay¹, Tomoyuki Okutsu², Anida Songnui³, Chanida Sakunrang¹,
Monwadee Wonglapsuwan^{1,2,*}

¹ Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hatyai, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

² Japan International Research Center for Agricultural Sciences, Tsukuba, Ibaraki 305-8686, Japan

³ Trang Coastal Fisheries Research and Development Center, Department of Fisheries, Trang 92150, Thailand

⁴ Center for Genomics and Bioinformatics Research, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hatyai, Songkhla, 90110, Thailand

* Corresponding author: monwadee.wo@gmail.com

Abstract: The banana shrimp (*Fenneropenaeus merguensis*) is economically significant in Thailand and is typically harvested from the wild. However, the increased harvesting of wild *F. merguensis* broodstock has led to a decline in both the quantity and quality of captured wild broodstock, along with a cumbersome management system. Gonad grafting has been explored as a method for preserving genetic material in various organisms, including fish. This study aimed to investigate gonad grafting in *F. merguensis*. A piece of banana shrimp ovary was stained with PKH26 red fluorescent dye and grafted into the second abdominal segment of *Litopenaeus vannamei*. One month after grafting, the fluorescent signal in the *L. vannamei* recipients was detected using chemiluminescence and fluorescence microscopy. Additionally, the grafted tissues were examined histologically. The results showed that the grafted ovaries remained within the muscles of the recipients even after one month. This is the first report of grafted tissue in shrimp. The study demonstrates the potential of using grafting techniques for shrimp gonads, which could be beneficial for genetic preservation in the future.

Keywords: *Fenneropenaeus merguensis*, *L. vannamei*, Grafting, Gonad Histology

Acknowledgments: This research was funded by the National Science, Research and Innovation Fund (NSRF) and Prince of Songkla University, Thailand, grant number SCI6601278S. Support was additionally received from the Japan Science and Technology Agency/Japan International Cooperation Agency, Science and Technology Research Partnership for Sustainable Development, SATREPS (JPMJSA 1806), Project for Utilization of Thailand Local Genetic Resources to Develop Novel Farmed Fish for Global Market (Thai Fish Project).

Poster Presentation - P2-05

Freezing for the Future: Cryopreservation Strategies for *Halophila ovalis*

Kuwanhusna Saroeng¹, and Monwadee Wonglapsuwan^{1,2,*}

¹Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

²Center for Genomics and Bioinformatics Research, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla 90110, Thailand

* Corresponding author: monwadee.wo@psu.ac.th

Abstract: In recent times, seagrass populations have significantly declined due to human activities such as coastal development, pollution, and climate change. Conservation efforts are crucial for protecting these vital ecosystems and preserving their ecological functions. Consequently, finding effective methods to preserve seagrass species at risk of extinction, such as through cryopreservation, is essential. This study focuses on the cryopreservation of *Halophila ovalis*, a seagrass species nearing extinction. Our objective is to explore various freezing methods to preserve different varieties of *H. ovalis*. We employed cryopreservation techniques using different cryoprotectants: Dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), glycerol, and ethylene glycol, at concentrations of 5%, 10%, and 15%. The samples were stored in liquid nitrogen for 24 hours. Cell viability and regeneration rates were assessed using FDA dye. Our results indicated that among the cryoprotectants and concentrations tested, 5% DMSO was the most effective, yielding a survival rate of 88.25% and a recovery percentage of 84.28%, compared to the control group. This research not only advances our understanding of seagrass preservation techniques but also offers a promising approach for conserving threatened seagrass species. By optimizing cryopreservation methods, we can better safeguard these crucial marine ecosystems and support their long-term survival and ecological function.

Keywords: Cryopreservation, Seagrass, Cryoprotectant, *Halophila ovalis*, Fluorescein Diacetate (FDA)

Acknowledgments: This research was funded by Plant Genetic Conservation Project Under the Royal Initiative of Her Royal Highness Princess Maha Chakri Sirindhorn (RSPG) and Prince of Songkla University, Thailand, grant number SCI6601002c.

POSTER PRESENTATION

Track 1

Biology,

Environment and Climate Change

Track 2

Biotechnology,

Biochemistry and Functional Food

Track 3

Bioactive

Natural Products and Biomedicine

Track 4

Bio-sensing

Technology and Data Science

Poster Presentation - P3-01

Lipid nanoparticles of germinated brown rice (*Oryza sativa* L. var. Sangyod) and chamomile (*Chamaemelum nobile* L.) to improve sleep quality and reduce stress in neurons (SH-SY5Y)

Danudate Tuntadapun^{1*}, Wuttikorn Phurivattanakul¹

¹ SMTE Project, Benchamarachuthit School, Nakhon Si Thammarat 80000, Thailand

* Corresponding author: Danudatet@gmail.com

Abstract: The negative impact of insomnia on cognitive function and overall health is what has sparked interest in GABA supplements as a way to promote stress reduction and better sleep. Moreover, apigenin from chamomile promotes sleep quality, and germinated brown rice's GABA strengthens immunity and encourages sleep. Nevertheless, stomach acid frequently breaks down GABA and it is not well absorbed. In this study, the benefits of GABA from three varieties of rice: Pattani Leb Nok, Sang Yod, and black sticky rice is compared, the best rice would be enhanced by combining chamomile flowers with two-phase extraction technology and an environmentally friendly green extraction approach to manufacture lipid nanoparticles from extracts of chamomile flowers and the rice. The components are refined using ultrasonication. O/W emulsion technology was then used to create these lipid nanoparticles. The assessment of SH-SY5Y nerve cells' survival rate concentrated on the extracts' capacity to stop cell death following oxidative stress caused by tert-butyl hydroperoxide exposure. The result in comparison to other rice varieties, tests showed that Sang Yod rice was the best germinated brown rice with less toxicity and supported a higher nerve cell density. Green extraction using chamomile flowers and Sang Yod rice showed the highest level of cell protection effectiveness. Next, the highest decreases in oxidative stress and neuronal cell death were observed upon the production of lipid nanoparticles at dosages of 0.5% and 1% W/W. Finally, Sang Yod rice showed the least amount of damage to cells and, in combination with lipid nanoparticles derived from chamomile flowers and germinated brown rice, demonstrated prospective benefits for improving sleep quality and lowering stress levels. Additional investigation is required prior to actual implementation.

Keywords: Sang Yod rice Chamomile Flowers GABA Apigenin and Lipid nanoparticles

Acknowledgements: We acknowledge to Ms. Jantip Chulasek Mr. Thunwa Binlatch Mr. Panyawut Rattanaom and Premier Innova.

Poster Presentation - P3-02

Investigating Nucleus Accumbens Oscillations in Mice Following Acute MDMA Administration (10 mg/kg) Using LFP Recording

Pakavarin Khunphet^{1,3}, Ekkasit Kumarnsit^{2,3}, and Dania Cheaha^{1,3,*}

¹ Division of Biological Science (Biology Program), Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hatyai, Songkhla, 90110, Thailand

² Division of Health and Applied Sciences (Physiology), Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hatyai, Songkhla, 90110, Thailand

³ Biosignal Research Center for Health, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hatyai, Songkhla, 90110, Thailand

* Corresponding author: dania.c@psu.ac.th

Abstract:

MDMA (3,4-methylenedioxymethamphetamine), commonly known as ecstasy, is a psychoactive drug with stimulant and hallucinogenic properties that enhance sociability, empathy, and mood, making it popular in recreational settings. An addictive effect of MDMA significantly impacts the nucleus accumbens (NAc), a key region in the brain's reward system. Elevation of dopamine level in the NAc is closely related to the drug's rewarding and addictive properties. However, the mechanism underlying how MDMA influences neural activity with the reward brain circuit remained unknown. To study the effects of MDMA on this brain circuit, neural oscillatory patterns associated with an intraperitoneal injection of MDMA (10 mg/kg) in mice were investigated. We used local field potential (LFP) recordings to measure synchronized electrical activity in the NAc over 1 hour after MDMA administration. These recordings provided insight into how MDMA alters neural oscillations and network communication within the NAc. Our findings indicate that MDMA administration leads to changes in LFP patterns in the NAc compared to the control group (saline administered). These changes highlight the influence of the drug on neural oscillations and the brain's reward system. Furthermore, investigating the underlying neurochemical mechanisms, comparing MDMA with other psychoactive substances, and developing therapeutic interventions to mitigate its adverse effects will further our understanding of the impact of MDMA and its potential for addiction.

Keywords: Acute MDMA, Local field potential, Nucleus Accumbens

Acknowledgments: This work was funded by the Graduate School, Prince of Songkla University, Faculty of Science Research Fund

Poster Presentation - P3-03

The Synergistic Effect of Lupinifolin and Antibiotics Against MRSA: A Potential Solution to Antibiotic Resistance

Sutthisa Khwankaew¹, Nantiya Joycharat², and Wipawadee Sianglum^{1,*}

¹ Division of Microbiology, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkhla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla, Thailand

² Faculty of Traditional Thai Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla, Thailand

* Corresponding author: wipawadee.s@psu.ac.th

Abstract: Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) is a leading cause of healthcare-associated infections. Increased antibiotic resistance limits treatment options, prolongs hospital stays and increases healthcare costs. Additionally, MRSA can lead to severe morbidity and mortality. Combining antibiotics with natural compounds is an alternative method to combat antibiotic resistance. Lupinifolin is an important bioactive compound isolated from *Albizia myriophylla* Benth. wood with various biological activities. This study evaluated the synergistic antibacterial activities of lupinifolin in combination with selected antibiotics against MRSA using broth microdilution method and time-kill assay. Synergistic antibacterial activities were performed using the checkerboard assay. Gene expression alteration after treatment was observed by qRT-PCR. The MIC of lupinifolin against *S.aureus* ATCC25923 and MRSA were 8 µg/ml. The MICs of streptomycin, chloramphenicol, and ciprofloxacin against *S.aureus* ATCC25923 and MRSA were 4 µg/ml, 8 µg/ml, and 0.5-1 µg/ml, respectively. Synergistic effects were observed only in combining lupinifolin and streptomycin against *S.aureus* ATCC25923 and MRSA (FIC =0.5). The time-kill curve of *S. aureus* ATCC25923 showed a significant decrease of more than 2 log after treatment with lupinifolin combined with streptomycin at 4 h to inhibit completely. *sarA*, a biofilm formation-related gene, showed significant down-regulation after treatment with the combination. This study showed effective antimicrobial and antibiofilm formation activities of lupinifolin in combination with antibiotics against *S. aureus*, particularly MRSA.

Keywords: Combination, Lupinifolin, Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, Synergistic effect

Acknowledgments: This work was funded by Prince of Songkla University grant, Contract No. SCI6302099S and Graduate Fellowship (Bachelor – Master), Faculty of Science Research Fund, Prince of Songkla University

POSTER PRESENTATION

Track 1

Biology,

Environment and Climate Change

Track 2

Biotechnology,

Biochemistry and Functional Food

Track 3

Bioactive

Natural Products and Biomedicine

Track 4

Bio-sensing

Technology and Data Science

Poster Presentaion - P4-01

Development of No-Code Programming to Implement 3D Animation for Telerehabilitation of Therapeutic Office Syndrome

Inarm Ekakkaraphibal¹, Lertpisit Sukapibul¹, Amornrat Chookliang^{2*} and Panu Thainira-mit^{3*}

¹ PSU Witthayanusorn School, Hat Yai, Songkhla, 90110, Thailand

² PSU Cadaveric Surgical Training Center, Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla, 90110, Thailand

³ Division of Physical Science (Physics), Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, Hat Yai, Songkhla, 90110, Thailand

* Corresponding author: panu.t@psu.ac.th

Abstract:

Office syndrome, a prevalent form of work-related musculoskeletal disorders among sedentary professionals, arises from prolonged sitting and improper posture, leading to discomfort and pain in areas such as the cervical, scapular, and lumbar regions. Stretching exercises are effective in preventing and alleviating these symptoms in office workers. This study was to examine the development and effectiveness of a 3D animated therapeutic application, designed to reduce the risk of incorrect exercise executions in workers with office syndrome. The application was developed using the Bubble.io platform, chosen for its rapid prototyping capabilities and ease of development. Despite the platform's limitations in supporting advanced customization, the core functionality of the app provided users with a seamless and intuitive interface that allowed them to identify specific areas of discomfort and pain. Upon selection, the app chose customized exercise regimens tailored to the user's needs, which offered precise guidance through interactive 3D animations. The visual instructions were complemented by auditory guidance and detailed captions to ensure clinical accuracy in each exercise and prevent the injuries from improper exercise executions. The system also incorporated feedback mechanisms for users to track their progress and adjust physical therapy exercises, ensuring a dynamic and adaptive therapeutic experience. This application was validated by physical therapists and domain experts for both safety and efficacy of therapeutic standards. The 3D application with auditory cues and principle of telerehabilitation enhanced user engagement and adherenced to therapeutic protocols for office syndrome. The study's findings underscored the effectiveness of this confluence of telerehabilitation and 3D animated therapeutic innovation. The no-code application can emerge as a compelling and effective tool for office workers. This 3D animated application can be a practical solution for alleviating musculoskeletal pain, enhancing muscular strength, and proactively addressing the risk factors related to office syndrome.

Keywords: Work-related musculoskeletal disorders, Office syndrome, Physical therapy exercises, 3D animation, Telerehabilitation

Acknowledgments: This project was supported by the Science Classroom in University Affiliated School (SCiUS). The funding of SCiUS was provided by the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, Research and Innovation.

LIST OF CONFERENCE ATTENDEES

Presenters

Code	Name - Last name	Type	Track	Title	email
KN1	Prof. Dr. Chatchai Muanprasat	Oral Presentation	Keynote Session	Exploring Frontiers in Bioscience Research	chatchai.mua@mahidol.ac.th
KN2	Asst. Prof. Dr. Sara Bumrungsri	Oral Presentation	Keynote Session	Bioscience Innovations for a Sustainable Tomorrow	sara.b@psu.ac.th
KN3	Prof. Dr. Snežana Maletić	Oral Presentation	Keynote Session	Organic Soil Amendments: Pollution Solution or Environmental Risk	snezana.maletic@dh.uns.ac.rs
KN4	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Surapong Chatpun	Oral Presentation	Keynote Session	Sharing Experience with Staff Exchange in Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON)	surapong.c@psu.ac.th
INV1-T1	Prof. Dr. Bojana Bokić	Oral Presentation	Biology	Traditional use of mints in SE Europe	bojana.bokic@dbe.uns.ac.rs
INV2-T2	Dr. Danijela Arsenov	Oral Presentation	Biotechnology	Beyond Simple Food – Unveiling the Medicinal Benefits and Human Health Risks of Apiaceae Species	danijela.arsenov@dbe.uns.ac.rs
INV3-T3	Dr. Muhammad Danial Bin Che Ramli	Oral Presentation	Bioactive Natural Products and Biomedicine	From Forest to Pharma: The Potential Effects of Natural Products in Neurological Disorder	muhddanial_cheramli@msu.edu.my
INV4-T4	Prof. Dr. Purim Jarujamrus	Oral Presentation	Bio-sensing Technology and Data Science	Tailored Functional Nanomaterials as Peroxidase Mimics on Microfluidic Paper-Based Analytical Devices	purim.j@ubu.ac.th, prim310@hotmail.com

Presenters

Code	Name - Last name	Type	Track	Title	email
				(μ PADs) for Innovative Point-of-Care Applications	
INV5	Ms. Gordana Vlahović	Oral Presentation	Horizon Session	Horizon Europe Funding Opportunities: Guidelines for Application	gordanav@uns.ac.rs
INV6	Mrs. Khobkhul Inieam	Oral Presentation	Erasmus Session	Erasmus+ Capacity Building in Higher Education: opportunities for universities and staff	Khobkhul.INIEAM@eeas.europa.eu
INV7	Ms. Ivana Pejović	Oral Presentation	Erasmus Session	EU/Erasmus+ projects: How to get involved?	ivana.pejovic@pmf.uns.ac.rs
OR1-01	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Viviana Maresca	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biology	Pilot study on the use of two different environmental pollution bioindicators, moss and bee, in an area with a high cancer incidence	viviana.maresca@unina.it
OR1-02	Dr. Milica Stankovic	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biology	From student exchange to climate change	milica.s@psu.ac.th
OR1-03	Ms. Sirinya Sirimahawan	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biology	The quality of sea grape growth in culture pond related to the seasonal change	s.sirimahawan68@gmail.com

Presenters

Code	Name - Last name	Type	Track	Title	email
OR1-04	Ms.UMI NATRA SHAHARUDIN	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biology	CYTOGENETICS AND GENOME SIZE ESTIMATION OF THE NARROW-LIP SPATHOGLOTTIS <i>AUREA</i> LINDL. (ORCHIDACEAE) FROM PENINSULAR MALAYSIA	uminatra98@gmail.com
OR1-05	Ms.Siti Nadia Binti Mohd Nizam	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biology	SURVIVAL STRATEGIES OF EPIPHYTIC AND LITHOPHYTIC ORCHIDS: EXPLORING THEIR ECOLOGICAL PARTNERSHIP WITH LICHENS IN DIVERSE ECOSYSTEMS	nadianizam25@student.usm.my
OR1-06	Mr.Farhan Rashid	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biology	Morphometric analysis of <i>Spathoglottis plicata</i> and <i>Spathoglottis plicata</i> var. <i>alba</i>	farhanrashids@student.usm.my
OR1-08	Ms.Kwansuda Kongthong	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biology	Recycling fish scale waste into high value-added products	kwansuda1999@gmail.com
OR1-09	Mrs.Rubaiya Pervin	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biology	Impacts of fish cage farming on underlying sediments and macrofauna of Songkhla Lagoon System, Southern Thailand	rubaiya2015@hstu.ac.bd

Presenters

Code	Name - Last name	Type	Track	Title	email
OR1-10	Ms.Sinjai Phetcharat	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biology	Heavy metal concentration in seaweed and seagrasses from the Andaman coastal areas: A case study from Lidee Island and Libong Island	s.phetcharat087@gmail.com
OR1-11	Ms.Phutita Wongwaiyut	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biology	A New Species of <i>Hipposideros</i> from Southeast Asia: Integrative Taxonomic Approach Reveals Cryptic Diversity	phutita9201@gmail.com
OR1-12	Mr.Pattanapong Jaisue	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biology	Increase in leaf greenness is an adaptative strategy of rice to P deficiency	6610220056@email.psu.ac.th
OR2-01	Dr. Nemanja Teslić	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biotechnology	Green solutions for recovery of secondary me-tabolites compounds	nemanja.teslic@fins.uns.ac.rs
OR2-02	Dr.Thunchanok Yaikhan	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biotechnology	Genomic Characterization and Phylogenetic Analysis of <i>Enterocloster aldenensis</i> PSU25A: An Opportunistic Pathogen in Southern Thailand	p_rair@hotmail.com
OR2-03	Mr.Pavarish Jantorn	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biotechnology	Colorimetric recombinase polymerase amplifi-cation for rapid detection of <i>Staphylococcus pseudintermedius</i>	pavarish.j@gmail.com

Presenters

Code	Name - Last name	Type	Track	Title	email
OR2-04	Ms.jirasa boonsan	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biotechnology	Thorough Screening of Potential Probiotics Using Nanopore Sequencing and Bioinformatic Analy-sis	6210210236@psu.ac.th
OR2-05	Ms.Thitaporn Dechathai	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biotechnology	Unveiling Mobile Genetic Elements: In-Depth Genomic Analysis of Multidrug-Resistant <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> PA12	oumthitaporn2543@gmail.com
OR2-06	Ms.Siriwan Kompramool	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biotechnology	Genomic Analysis and Probiotic Characteristics of <i>Pediococcus pentosaceus</i> HN8 with a Focus on GABA Synthesis	siriwantal13@gmail.com
OR2-07	Ms.Thanchanok Muangkaew	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biotechnology	Phenotypic and Genomic Analysis of <i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i> MEDPSU_PRO_001 isolated from Chicken Feces, a potential probiotic with aggregation ability	swan062544@gmail.com
OR2-08	Ms.Krittaporn Lempan	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Biotechnology	The Genetic Diversity and Population Study of Mahseer, <i>Tor tambra</i> and <i>Tor tambroides</i> Distributed in Thailand and Peninsular Malaysia	krittaporn.near1259@gmail.com

Presenters

Code	Name - Last name	Type	Track	Title	email
OR3-01	Assoc. Prof. Dr.Fazia Adyani Ahmad Fuad	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Bioactive Natural Products and Biomedicine	Exploring the Potential of Chitin and Its Derivative in Inhibiting the Human Hexokinase Isoform 2 Towards Developing Anti-Dengue Drugs	fazia_adyani@iium.edu.my
OR3-02	Ms.Piyapat Aiemcharoen	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Bioactive Natural Products and Biomedicine	Biological Activities of Ethanollic Extracts From the Inflorescence of Kluai Namwa (<i>Musa</i> ABB CV. "Kluai Namwa")	piyapat.aiem@gmail.com
OR4-01	Mr.Predrag Lugonaja	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Bio-sensing Technology and Data Science	A Decade of Crop Monitoring Through Remote Sensing: Insights into Climate Change Impacts on crop practice, case studies Vojvodina from 2013- 2023	lugonjap@biosense.rs
OR4-02	Dr.Mohd Zulhakimi Ab Razak	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Bio-sensing Technology and Data Science	Design Challenges in the Development of Portable Peritoneal Dialysis Prototype Module in Malaysia	zul.hakimi@ukm.edu.my
OR4-03	Dr.Atchara Lomae	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Bio-sensing Technology and Data Science	Smartphone-enabled electrochemical point-of-care testing for SARS-CoV-2 detection	Atchara.lo@psu.ac.th

Presenters

Code	Name - Last name	Type	Track	Title	email
OR4-04	Dr.Suntisak Khumngern	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Bio-sensing Technology and Data Science	Smartphone-enabled flow injection amperometric glucose monitoring based on a screen- printed carbon electrode modified with PEDOT@PB and a GOx@PPtNPs@MWCNTs nanocomposite	suntisak.k@psu.ac.th
OR4-05	Mr.Thanawath Tuntiwongmetee	Abstract-Oral Presentation	Bio-sensing Technology and Data Science	Enzymatic uric acid biosensor based on AuNPs-GO-CS porous cryogel coated on PB- PEDOT:PSS modified screen- printed carbon electrode	u8yg6pop@hotmail.com
P1-01	Asst. Prof. Dr.Bongkot Wichachucherd	Abstract-Poster Presentation	Biology	Year-round Occurrence of Crustacean Holoplanktons in Mae Klong River Mouth as Indicator of Natural Food in Gulf of Thailand	bongkot.w@ku.th
P1-02	Prof. Dr.Slobodanka Pajević	Abstract-Poster Presentation	Biology	Heavy metals accumulation (As, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, Cu and Cd) in vegetables grown on polluted soil and consumers health assessment	slobodanka.pajevic@dbe.uns.ac.rs
P1-03	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Adriana Basile	Abstract-Poster Presentation	Biology	Combining the use of Mosses and Snails as Bio-indicators of Heavy Metal Air Pollution	adbasile@unina.it

Presenters

Code	Name - Last name	Type	Track	Title	email
P1-04	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Viviana Maresca	Abstract-Poster Presentation	Biology	Protective effect of <i>Ocimum basilicum</i> L. essential oil on <i>Lactuca sativa</i> L. treated with cadmium	viviana.maresca@unina.it /mesensunisa@gmail.com
P1-05	Ms.Rapeepan Kongnual	Abstract-Poster Presentation	Biology	Effect of Chronic High-Sugar Consumption on Behavior Adaptation in Mice	rapeepan689@gmail.com
P1-06	Asst. Prof. Dr.Yurachat Meksuwan	Abstract-Poster Presentation	Biology	Influence of Seasonal Variations on the Anatom-ical and Physiological Characteristics of <i>Launaea sarmentosa</i> (Willd.) Kuntze (Asteraceae) of the Andaman Coast, Thailand	yurachat.y@phuket.psu.ac.th
P2-01	Ms. Gordana Vlahović (Asst. Prof. Dr.Anita Leovac Maćerak)	Abstract-Poster Presentation	Biotechnology	Acetic acid pretreatment effects on biogas production from sewage sludge	anita.leovac@dh.uns.ac.rs
P2-02	Ms.Sirikan Suwannasin	Abstract-Poster Presentation	Biotechnology	Phenotypic and Genotypic Study Through Virulence and Antibiotic Resistance of <i>Enterococcus avium</i> MC09 from Mud Crab	suwannasinsirikan@gmail.com
P2-03	Ms.Nattarika Chaichana	Abstract-Poster Presentation	Biotechnology	The Whole Genome Analysis of <i>Mangrovibacter phragmitis</i> PSU-3885-11 Isolated from a Patient in Thailand	naampueng_np@hotmail.com

Presenters

Code	Name - Last name	Type	Track	Title	email
P2-04	Ms.Jaruwan Boonchuay	Abstract-Poster Presentation	Biotechnology	Germ cell grafting in banana shrimp for sus-tainable aquaculture	jaruwan.boonchuay@gmail.com
P2-05	Ms.Kuwanhusna Saroeng	Abstract-Poster Presentation	Biotechnology	Freezing for the Future: Cryopreservation Strategies for <i>Halophila ovalis</i>	kwhusna@gmail.com
P3-01	Mr.Danudate Tuntadapun	Abstract-Poster Presentation	Bioactive Natural Products and Biomedicine	Lipid nanoparticles of germinated brown rice (<i>Oryza sativa</i> L. var. Sangyod) and chamomile (<i>Chamaemelum nobile</i> L.) to improve sleep quality and reduce stress in neurons (SH-SY5Y)	Danudatet@gmail.com
P3-02	Ms.pakavarin khunphet	Abstract-Poster Presentation	Bioactive Natural Products and Biomedicine	Investigating Nucleus Accumbens Oscillations in Mice Following Acute MDMA Administration (10 mg/kg) Using LFP Recording	6610230031@email.psu.ac.th
P3-03	Ms.Sutthisa Khwankaew	Abstract-Poster Presentation	Bioactive Natural Products and Biomedicine	The Synergistic Effect of Lupinifolin and Antibiotics Against MRSA: A Potential Solution to Antibiotic Resistance	6610220023@email.psu.ac.th

Presenters

Code	Name - Last name	Type	Track	Title	email
P4-01	Mr.Inarm Ekakkaraphibal	Abstract-Poster Presentation	Bio-sensing Technology and Data Science	Development of No-Code Programming to Implement 3D Animation for Telerehabilitation of Therapeutic Office Syndrome	4949@psuwit.ac.th

General Participants

Name - Last name	Faculty	University	email
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Jutarut Iewkittayakorn	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	jpornpunyapat@yahoo.com
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Lompong Klinnawee	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	lompong.k@psu.ac.th
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Natthawan Sermwittayawong	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	natthawan.k@psu.ac.th
Asst. Prof. Dr. Krittika Kaewchumnong	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	krittika.k@psu.ac.th
Asst. Prof. Dr. Matsapume Detcharoen	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	matsapume.d@psu.ac.th
Asst. Prof. Dr. Rujinard Sriwoon	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	rujinard.s@psu.ac.th
Asst. Prof. Dr. Kanchana Srinitiwara Wong	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	kanchana.w@psu.ac.th
Asst. Prof. Dr. Kringpaka Wangkulangkul	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	kringpaka.w@psu.ac.th
Asst. Prof. Dr. Phuripong Meksuwan	Faculty of Science and Technology	Prince of Songkla University	phuripong.m@pkru.ac.th
Dr. Sawitree Dueramae	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	sawitree.d@psu.ac.th
Dr. Amornrat Chookliang	PSU Cadaveric Surgical Training Center	Prince of Songkla University	amornrat.chu@psu.ac.th
Dr. Kulwanit Patninan	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	kulwanit.p@gmail.com
Dr. Sompop Saeheng	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	sompop.s@psu.ac.th
Mr. Chanon Thongchum	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	Chanonnon.cn@gmail.com
Mr. Hao-Chen Tang	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	jeffrey19991125@gmail.com
Mr. Hatthachai Kaeosombun	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210349@psu.ac.th
Mr. Kanitsorn Srichai	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	kanitsorn1812@gmail.com
Mr. Khunanon Chanasongkhram	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	chanasongkhram.k@gmail.com
Mr. Mehraj Ahmad	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6710230003@psu.ac.th
Mr. Porawit Saraban	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210186@email.psu.ac.th
Mr. Prasert Yodsawat	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	prasert0524@gmail.com
Mr. Rofi-ee Ja-oh	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	rofiee.jaoh@gmail.com
Mr. Sai Nay Htut Kyaw	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	nayhtutkyaw.myi@gmail.com

General Participants

Name - Last name	Faculty	University	email
Mr.Teerapat Romgate	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	teerapatsadada@gmail.com
Mrs.Atchima Tantiphathon	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210691@email.psu.ac.th
Mrs.Chalisa Pantalay	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210077@psu.ac.th
Mrs.Oranit Sriwichian	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	queenoranit12@gmail.com
Mrs.Sunainah Samaesaree	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210668@email.psu.ac.th
Mrs.Tanadda Chumpoosang	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210500@psu.ac.th
Mrs.Thongkamol Thongfueang	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210116@psu.ac.th
Ms.Aroonchai Amera	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	bbaeblue00@gmail.com
Ms.Chanida Sakunrang	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	chanida.b97@gmail.com
Ms.Fitrah Mataeha	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210758@psu.ac.th
Ms.Ingkarat Sitthisak	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210706@psu.ac.th
Ms.Kannika Aphaiphong	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210009@email.psu.ac.th
Ms.Kanyarat Kalajak	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210398@psu.ac.th
Ms.Kornkanok Kamutchat	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210394@psu.ac.th
Ms.Kotcharat Thipsukumpiti	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210390@psu.ac.th
Ms.Lining Manor	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210622@psu.ac.th
Ms.Mareena Muenpan	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210591@psu.ac.th
Ms.Marisa Boontaworn	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	marisa.b@psu.ac.th
Ms.Nannalin Khamcharoen	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210160@psu.ac.th
Ms.Nareenath Muneerungsee	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	nareenath.m@psu.ac.th
Ms.Nareerat Kumnuanjit	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	nareerat.knj@gmail.com
Ms.Nattika Sripeng	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210513@email.psu.ac.th
Ms.Nittaya Jaeram	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	nittayaramj@gmail.com
Ms.Panchalika Deachamag	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	dpanchalika@gmail.com
Ms.Pandharee Srisong	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6310210244@psu.ac.th

General Participants

Name - Last name	Faculty	University	email
Ms.Phinphicha Thummalee	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210749@psu.ac.th
Ms.Pimlapas Suravee	Biomedical science and Biomedical Engineering	Prince of Songkla University	pimlapas.svee@gmail.com
Ms.Piyaporn Puntti	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6610220054@psu.ac.th
Ms.Rosada Hayiasen	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210267@psu.ac.th
Ms.Rungnapa Pichaikarn	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	tikpichaikal@gmail.com
Ms.Sophita Rodruksa	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6610220033@email.psu.ac.th
Ms.Sriwilai Jaidee	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	Sriwilai.102@gmail.com
Ms.Suchada Nukhong	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210664@email.psu.ac.th
Ms.Supada Nuinamwong	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	supada.nw@gmail.com
Ms.Suparat Chumchuad	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210671@psu.ac.th
Ms.Supawadee Yuttitham	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210672@psu.ac.th
Ms.Suprawee Wongtechanon	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	hongissaree@gmail.com
Ms.Suttida Saewong	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	suttida.2541.ss@gmail.com
Ms.Suwimol Sae-wong	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	ss.suwimoleve@gmail.com
Ms.Thandar Maung Maung	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6710220083@psu.ac.th
Ms.Tharnthip Pitaktham	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6610230032@email.psu.ac.th
Ms.Theerisara Klahan	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6610220077@psu.ac.th
Ms.Thitima Ninrat	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	6410210141@psu.ac.th
Ms.Vianchanu Promjinno	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	vianchanu@gmail.com
Ms.Waranchalee Chimpet	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	beemy0615@gmail.com
Ms.Yanisa Chomchuen	Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University	mimiecream@hotmail.com

COMMITTEES

Conference Committees

Name-Surname	Position / Department	Organization
National Steering Committee		
Asst. Prof. Dr. Niwat Keawpradub	President	Prince of Songkla University
Asst. Prof. Dr. Thakerng Wongsirichot	Vice President for Academic and International Affairs	Prince of Songkla University
Prof. Dr. Anchana Prathep	Dean, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Pimonsri Mittraparp-Arthorn	Associate Dean for Academic Affairs and International Relations	Prince of Songkla University, Faculty of Science
Asst. Prof. Dr. Boonyarit Chatthong	Associate Dean for Research, Innovation and Public Relations	Prince of Songkla University, Faculty of Science
Asst. Prof. Dr. Pornsuda Bomlai	Associate Dean for Administration	Prince of Songkla University, Faculty of Science
Asst. Prof. Dr. Jarunee Duangsuwan	Associate Dean for Information Technology and Education Support	Prince of Songkla University, Faculty of Science
Ms. Jittima Phoesena	Head of International Relations Office	Prince of Songkla University, Faculty of Science
Ms. Sunisa Meesen	International Relations Officer	Prince of Songkla University, Faculty of Science
Ms. Anna Chatthong	International Relations Officer	Prince of Songkla University, Faculty of Science
International Steering Committee		
Prof. Dr. Srđan Rončević	Dean, Faculty of Sciences UNS	University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
Prof. Dr. Slobodanka Pajevic	Full Professor	University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia

Name-Surame	Position / Department	Organization
Prof. Dr. Neda Mimica Dukić	Full Professor	University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
Prof. Dr. Anamarija Mandić	Senior Researcher	University of Novi Sad, Institute of Food Technology, Serbia
Dr. Oskar Marko	Head of the Center for Information Technologies	University of Novi Sad, BioSense Institute, Serbia
Ms. Gordana Vlahović	Head of International Relations Office	University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
Ms. Ivana Pejović	International Relations Officer	University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
Scientific Commitees		
Asst. Prof. Dr. Boonyarit Chatthong	Division of Physical Science	Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Pimonsri Mittraparp-arthorn	Division of Biological Science	Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Jaruwan Mayakun	Division of Biological Science	Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Monwadee Wonglapsuwan	Division of Biological Science	Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University
Asst. Prof. Dr. Wipawadee Sianglum	Division of Biological Science	Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Apon Numnuam	Division of Physical Science	Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University
Dr. Kittirat Phooplub	Division of Physical Science	Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Chongdee Buranachai	Division of Physical Science	Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University
Asst. Prof. Dr. Chinnapong Angsuchotmetee	Division of Computational Science	Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University

Name-Surname	Position / Department	Organization
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Decha Sermwittayawong	Division of Health and Applied Sciences	Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Kitichate Sridith	Division of Biological Science	Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Sahut Chantanaorrapint	Division of Biological Science	Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Pilaiwanwadee Hutamekalin	Division of Health and Applied Sciences	Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University
Asst. Prof. Dr. Wandee Udomuksorn	Division of Health and Applied Sciences	Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Nataša Simin	Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection	Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad
Prof. Dr. Milan Borišev	Department of Biology and Ecology	Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad
Prof. Dr. Dejan Orčić	Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection	Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad
Asst. Prof. Dr. Danijela Arsenov	Department of Biology and Ecology	Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad
Asst. Prof. Dr. Emilija Svirčev	Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection	Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad
Prof. Dr. Jelica Simeunović	Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection	Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad
Prof. Dr. Jasna Mastilović	BioSense Institute	University of Novi Sad
Prof. Dr. Nataša Nikolić	Department of Biology and Ecology	Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad
Asst. Prof. Dr. Bojana Bokić	Department of Biology and Ecology	Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad

Name-Surname	Position / Department	Organization
Prof. Dr. Marija Lesijak	Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection	Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad
Prof. Dr. Jadranka Luković	Department of Biology and Ecology	Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad
Prof. Dr. Goran Anačkov	Department of Biology and Ecology	Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad
Prof. Dr. Mihajla Đan	Department of Biology and Ecology	Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad
Dr. Vasa Radonic	BioSense Institute	University of Novi Sad
Dr. Pavle Jovanov	Institute of Food Technology	University of Novi Sad
Prof. Dr. Sari Kontunen-Soppela	Department of Environmental and Biological Sciences	University of Eastern Finland, Joensuu, Finland
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Carmen Arena	Department of Biology	University of Naples Federico II, Italy
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Adriana Basile	Department of Biology	University of Naples Federico II, Italy
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Gianluca Polese	Department of Biology,	University of Naples Federico II, Italy
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Viviana Maresca	Department of Life Sciences, Health and Health Profession	University of Rome "link Campus", Rome, Italy
Prof. Dr. Valerija Dunkić	Department of Biology, Faculty of Science	University of Split, Croatia
Prof. Dr. Slobodanka Pajević	Department of Biology and Ecology	Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad
Dr. Anamarija Mandić	Institute of Food Technology	University of Novi Sad

Name-Surame	Position / Department	Organization
Reviewers		
Track 1: Biology, Environment and Climate Change		
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Jaruwat Mayakun	Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University
Prof. Dr. Milan Borišev	Faculty of Sciences	University of Novi Sad
Prof. Dr. Nataša Nikolić	Faculty of Sciences	University of Novi Sad
Dr. Yingyot Lapwong	Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University
Asst. Prof. Dr. Patamarerk Engsontia	Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University
Dr. Ekkalak Rattanachot	Excellence Center for Biodiversity of Peninsular Thailand	Prince of Songkla University
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Kitichate Sridith	Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University
Track 2: Biotechnology, Biochemistry and Functional Food		
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Monwadee Wonglapsuwan	Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University
Prof. Dr. Anamarija Mandić	Institute for Food Technology, FINS	University of Novi Sad
Prof. Dr. Slobodanka Pajević	Faculty of Sciences	University of Novi Sad
Prof. Dr. Alex Hon-Tsen Yu	Department of Life Science,	National Taiwan University, Taipei
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Warapond Wanna	Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Wiriya Loongyai	Department of Animal Science	Kasetsart University
Asst. Prof. Dr. Suchera Thananimit	Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Komwit Surachat	Department of Biomedical Sciences and Biomedical Engineering	Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University

Name-Surame	Position / Department	Organization
Track 3: Bioactive Natural Products and Biomedicine		
Asst. Prof. Dr. Wipawadee Sianglum	Division of Biological Science, Faculty of Science,	Prince of Songkla University
Prof. Dr. Marija Lesijak	Faculty of Sciences	University of Novi Sad
Prof. Dr. Dejan Orčić	Faculty of Sciences	University of Novi Sad
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Juraithip Wungsintaweekul	Department of Pharmacognosy and Pharmaceutical Botany, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences	Prince of Songkla University
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Suda Chakthong	Division of Physical Science, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University
Asst. Prof. Dr. Yaowapa Sukpondma	Division of Physical Science, Faculty of Science	
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Ekkasit Kumarnsit	Division of Health and Applied Sciences, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Pilaiwanwadee Hutamekalin	Division of Health and Applied Sciences, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University
Asst. Prof. Dr. Wandee Udomuksorn	Division of Health and Applied Sciences, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Wanida Suktetsiri	Division of Health and Applied Sciences, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University
Dr. Muhammad Danial Bin Che Ramli	Management and Science University, Malaysia	Management and Science University, Malaysia
Track 4: Bio-sensing Technology and Data Science		
Dr. Vasa Radonic	BioSense Institute	University of Novi Sad
Dr. Predrag Lugonja	BioSense Institute	University of Novi Sad

Name-Surname	Position / Department	Organization
Dr. Suntisak Khumngern	Division of Physical Science, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University
Dr. Atchara Lormae	Division of Physical Science, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Chittanon Buranachai	Division of Physical Science, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University
Dr. Kittirat Phooplub	Division of Physical Science, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University
Asst. Prof. Dr. Chidchanok Choksuchat	Division of Computational Science, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University
Asst. Prof. Dr. Kasikrit Damkliang	Division of Computational Science, Faculty of Science	Prince of Songkla University

IBSC
2024

